

Case definitions and data collection forms

Document information

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1. Introduction

The VAC4EU Validation Task Force (medically trained persons) developed the procedure for case definitions and ascertainment of level of certainty, which when available were based on Brighton Collaboration (BC) case definitions. The Validation Task Force used available data collection forms from SPEAC and adapted them to real world data. This document presents the final VAC4EU case definitions and data collection forms adapted from the Brighton Collaboration and SPEAC for the following sixteen adverse events of special interest (AESIs):

- Myocarditis and pericarditis
- Thrombosis with thrombocytopenia syndrome (TTS)
- Guillain-Barré syndrome (GBS)
- Anaphylaxis
- Idiopathic thrombocytopenia (ITP)
- Transverse myelitis
- Major congenital anomalies
- Narcolepsy
- Cerebral venous sinus thrombosis (CVST)
- Deep vein thrombosis (DVT)
- Pulmonary embolism (PE)
- Hemorrhagic stroke
- Ischemic stroke
- Meningoencephalitis including ADEM
- Bleeding with Thrombocytopenia (BT)

2. Myocarditis and pericarditis

The BC case definition for myocarditis and pericarditis used was

Sexson Tejtel SK, Munoz FM, Al-Ammouri I, Savorgnan F, Guggilla RK, Khuri-Bulos N, Phillips L, Engler RJM. Myocarditis and pericarditis: Case definition and guidelines for data collection, analysis, and presentation of immunization safety data. *Vaccine*. 2022;40(10):1499-1511. doi: 10.1016/j.vaccine.2021.11.074.

The VAC4EU data collection form was based on the SPEAC data collection:

Law, B. AESI Case Definition Companion Guide: Myocarditis and pericarditis. Zenodo; May 2022. DOI [10.5281/zenodo.6668894](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6668894).

Modifications, indicated in green, were made to make criteria more explicit and to make them suitable for real world data (RWD). The data collection form was subsequently adapted to REDCAP and automated logic was used to attribute a level of diagnostic certainty (LOC).

The following changes are implemented to the original Brighton Collaboration form:

- Two additional levels of certainty were established for Level 2 and Level 3, which expand on the existing framework provided by the Brighton collaboration. Each level was subdivided in two, i.e., Level 2-A, Level 2-B, Level 3-A, and Level 3-B.
- Level 2-A and Level 3-A use the criteria defined by the Brighton collaboration for Level 2 and Level 3, respectively. Level 2-B and Level 3-B maintain all the same criteria, except for the recorded absence of explicit details regarding each criteria.
- Additionally, Level 4 in the VAC4EU classification system was divided into two sublevels: Level 4-A and Level 4-B. Level 4-B aligns with the criteria established by the Brighton Collaboration. A case meet the Level 4-A case defintion only if was reported as myocarditis or pericarditis with insufficient evidence to meet LOC1-3. In addition, a LOC of Level 4-A was attributed if the diagnosis was made by a specialist, and a Level 4-B was attributed when the diagnosis was made by a non-specialist. This sublevel recognizes the expertise and clinical judgment of the specialist in diagnosing myocarditis, taking into account the context of limited evidence.
- To provide further clarity regarding certain criteria, footnotes were included in the data collection form with corresponding references to improve abstractors' understanding of the criteria and accurately interpret them. These references contain values that can be used to define normal ranges for various markers, such as C-reactive protein (CRP), high-sensitivity CRP (hs-CRP), erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR), creatine kinase MB (CK-MB), total Troponin, Troponin I, troponin T, and high-sensitivity troponin.
- Additionally, we expanded the cardiac and inflammatory markers section to also include total troponin, high-sensitivity troponin, and hs-CRP. We believe that if these markers show abnormalities, they hold equal significance and should be reported alongside troponin I, troponin T, and CRP. From a logical standpoint, the level of diagnostic certainty remains consistent regardless of whether troponin T, troponin I, total troponin, or hs-troponin is used. Similarly, the logic of the level of certainty remains unchanged regardless of whether CRP or hs-CRP is used.

By including these markers and their corresponding footnotes, we aimed to provide comprehensive information and ensure that important diagnostic criteria were considered in the assessment process. This approach allowed for a more comprehensive evaluation of cases and enhanced the overall accuracy and reliability of the classification system.

Table 1. Myocarditis and pericarditis data abstraction form

Record specific information, that is as complete as possible, for all rows in the table below. The red font identifies specific criteria related to the myocarditis and/or pericarditis case definitions.

1. Date of illness onset			
2. Hospital admission?			
3. Admitting diagnosis:			
4. Discharge diagnosis:			
5. Criterion A1: Cardiac symptoms	1. Acute chest pain or pressure 2. Palpitations 3. Dyspnea at rest, with exercise or lying down	4. Diaphoresis 5. Sudden death 6. None of the above	7. Unknown if any of 1-5 present or absent
Criterion A-2: Non-specific symptoms: adults & older children (12 years or older)	1. Dizziness or syncope 2. Abdominal pain 3. Fatigue 4. Edema 5. Cough 6. Nausea, vomiting +/- diarrhoea	7. Shoulder or upper back pain 8. Weakness 9. Cyanosis 10. Altered mental status 11. Low grade intermittent fever ($\geq 38.0^{\circ}\text{C}$)	12. None of the above 13. Unknown if any of 1-11 present or absent
7. Criterion A-3: Non-specific symptoms: Infants & younger children 11 years or younger	1. Poor feeding 2. Vomiting 3. Lethargy	4. Tachypnea 5. Irritability 6. None of the above	7. Unknown if any of 1-5 present or absent
Criterion A-4: combination of A1 and A2	1- Confirmed myocarditis symptoms by specialist, but unknown in details	2- Confirmed pericarditis symptoms by specialist, but unknown in details	
Criterion B: Physical exam features	1. Pericardial friction rub 2. Pulsus paradoxus	3. Distant heart sounds (infants & children) 4. None of the above	5. Unknown if any of 1-3 present or absent 6. confirmed physical exam confirming pericarditis, without details by specialist*

<p>9. Criterion C: Inflammatory Markers Were there any biomarkers supporting evidence of inflammation? (check all that apply)</p>	<p>0. None tested, or tested but no results or unknown if tested</p> <p>1. ESR elevated (highest measured value) abnormal ESR :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Men under 50 years old: less than 15 mm/hr • Men over 50 years old: less than 20 mm/hr • Women under 50 years old: less than 20 mm/hr • Women over 50 years old: less than 30 mm/hr • Child ≤10mm/hr • Newborn: 0-2 mm/hr <p>2. CRP elevated (highest measured value: ¹ abnormal CRP: CRP above 10 mg/L</p> <p>3. High sensitivity (hs) CRP elevated (highest measured value: hsCRP> 3 mg/L)</p> <p>4. D-dimer elevated (highest measured value:</p> <p>5. None of the above (choose this option if whichever ones were tested, were within normal range)</p> <p>6-Confirmed positive inflammatory marker confirming myocarditis without details by specialist*.</p>
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¹ Lee Y, McKechnie T, Doumouras AG, Handler C, Eskicioglu C, Gmora S, Anvari M, Hong D. Diagnostic Value of C-Reactive Protein Levels in Postoperative Infectious Complications After Bariatric Surgery: a Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Obes Surg.* 2019 Jul;29(7):2022-2029. [[PubMed](#)]

Johns I, Moschonas KE, Medina J, Ossei-Gerning N, Kassianos G, Halcox JP. Risk classification in primary prevention of CVD according to QRISK2 and JBS3 'heart age', and prevalence of elevated high-sensitivity C reactive protein in the UK cohort of the EURIKA study. *Open Heart.* 2018;5(2):e000849. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)]

<p>10. Criteria D1+D2: Cardiac biomarkers Were any myocardial biomarkers measured and if so were they elevated or normal? (check all that apply)</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 0. None tested, or tested but no results or unknown if tested 1. D1.1. Troponin T elevated (highest measured value: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • normal Troponin-T in different references ≤ 0.2 ng/mL 2. D1.2 Troponin I elevated (highest measured value: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Troponin-I: positive levels ranged from 0.5 ng/ml to 50 ng/ml • Total troponin: High: >0.40 ng/ml 3. D2 Creatine Kinase Myocardial Band (CK-MB) elevated (highest measured value: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ normal CK-MB in 2 sources: Normal = 5 to 25 IU/L ○ CK – MB = 0 to 5 $\mu\text{g/L}$² 4. Normal troponin 5. Normal CK-MB 6- Confirmed elevated cardiac biomarkers confirming myocarditis/pericarditis, without details by specialist*
<p>11. Criterion E: Electrocardiogram (ECG) abnormalities ECG results relevant to myocarditis and/or pericarditis. Read carefully and check all that apply based on available ECG reports done during the illness AV = atrioventricular</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 0. ECG not done, or done but no results available or unknown if done 1. Paroxysmal or sustained atrial or ventricular arrhythmias (premature atrial or ventricular beats, and/or supraventricular or ventricular tachycardia, interventricular conduction delay, abnormal Q waves, low voltages, Sinus tachycardia, SVT, atrial fibrillation, PVCs, VT, VF) 2. AV nodal conduction delays or intraventricular conduction defects (AV block (grade I-III), new bundle branch block) 3. Continuous ambulatory ECG monitoring that detects frequent atrial or ventricular ectopy 4. ST-segment or T-wave abnormalities (elevation or inversion) 5. Newly reduced r-wave height, low voltage, or abnormal q waves 6. Premature atrial and premature ventricular contractions (PACs, PVCs) 7. Diffuse concave-upward ST-segment elevation 8. ST-segment depression in aVR (ECG electrode lead placed on R arm) 9. PR-depression throughout the leads without reciprocal ST-segment changes 10. Nonspecific abnormalities other than those listed above (describe: like Tachycardia) 11. No abnormalities seen on ECG 12-Confirmed ECG abnormality conforming myocarditis without details by specialist* 13-Confirmed ECG abnormality conforming pericarditis without details by specialist*

² <https://labpedia.net/cardiac-marker-part-2-ck-mb-cardiac-enzyme/#:~:text=CK%20DMB%20significance%3A,onset%20of%20acute%20myocardial%20infarction.>

<p>12. Criterion F: Echocardiogram abnormalities</p> <p>Echocardiogram results relevant to myocarditis and/or pericarditis. Read carefully and check all that apply based on available echocardiogram reports.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 0. Echocardiogram not done, or done but no results or unknown if done 1. New focal or diffuse left or right ventricular function abnormalities (e.g. decreased ejection fraction) 2. Segmental wall motion abnormalities 3. Global systolic or diastolic function depression/abnormality (Decreased longitudinal and circumferential strain and strain rates on tissue Doppler) 4. Ventricular dilation 5. Wall thickness change 6. Evidence of abnormal fluid collection or pericardial inflammation 7. No abnormalities seen on echocardiogram 8. Confirmed echocardiogram confirming myocarditis without details by specialist* 9. Confirmed echocardiogram confirming pericarditis without details by specialist* 		
<p>13. Criterion G: Cardiac magnetic resonance (cMR) abnormalities</p> <p>CMR results relevant to myocarditis and/or pericarditis. Read carefully and check all that apply based on available cMR reports.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 0. 1. cMR not done, or done but no results or unknown if done 1. Edema on T2 weighted study, typically patchy in nature 2. 2. Late gadolinium enhancement on T1 weighted study with an increased enhancement ratio between myocardial and skeletal muscle, typically involving at least one non-ischemic regional distribution with recovery (myocyte injury) 3. 3. Evidence of abnormal fluid collection or pericardial inflammation 4. 4.No abnormalities seen 5. 5. Other abnormality. Describe: 6. Confirmed cMR confirming myocarditis without details by specialist* 7. Confirmed cMR confirming pericarditis without details by specialist* 		
<p>14. Criterion H: Chest MRI and/or CT abnormalities</p> <p>NOTE: one or the other of chest MRI and CT may have been done.</p>	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%; vertical-align: top;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Chest MRI and CT not done, or unknown if done, or no results available 2. Chest MRI or CT showed evidence of abnormal pericardial fluid collection or pericardial inflammation 3. Chest MRI and CT normal (choose this if only 1 test done but normal) </td> <td style="width: 50%; vertical-align: top;"> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Chest MRI and/or CT had abnormalities other than above. Describe: 5. Confirmed chest MRI and/or CT confirming pericarditis without details by specialist* </td> </tr> </table>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Chest MRI and CT not done, or unknown if done, or no results available 2. Chest MRI or CT showed evidence of abnormal pericardial fluid collection or pericardial inflammation 3. Chest MRI and CT normal (choose this if only 1 test done but normal) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Chest MRI and/or CT had abnormalities other than above. Describe: 5. Confirmed chest MRI and/or CT confirming pericarditis without details by specialist*
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Chest MRI and CT not done, or unknown if done, or no results available 2. Chest MRI or CT showed evidence of abnormal pericardial fluid collection or pericardial inflammation 3. Chest MRI and CT normal (choose this if only 1 test done but normal) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Chest MRI and/or CT had abnormalities other than above. Describe: 5. Confirmed chest MRI and/or CT confirming pericarditis without details by specialist* 		
<p>15. Criterion I: Chest X-ray (CXR) abnormalities</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 0. CXR not done, or unknown if done, or no results available 1. CXR abnormal showing enlarged heart 2. CXR normal 3. CXR had abnormalities other than enlarged heart. Describe 4. Confirmed CXR confirming pericarditis without details by specialist 		

<p>16. Criterion J: Cardiac tissue examination Histopathologic exam of cardiac tissues (autopsy or endomyocardial biopsy (check all that apply))</p>	<p>0. Not done, unknown if done or no results 1. Myocardial inflammation* 2. Pericardial inflammation* 3. No inflammation seen Describe the abnormalities seen: 4-confirmed tissue biopsy confrmring Myocarditis/Pericarditis withouth details by specialist*</p>
<p>Criterion X: Alternate diagnosis for cardiac findings. Alternate diagnosis/diagnoses for the cardiac findings exclude myocarditis or pericarditis as a diagnosis. The case definition doesn't require that investigation(s) be done for these entities, but any that are documented should be noted here. If there is a history of prior events it would also be good to capture but would need discussion with a physician to determine if it is an exclusion to myocarditis and/or pericarditis. (Check all that apply)</p>	<p>1. No alternate diagnosis identified 2. Systemic inflammatory disease. Specify: 3. Cardiac tumour (rhabdomyosarcoma) 4. Metastatic cancer. Specify: 5. Metabolic disorder (e.g. hypothyroidism, renal failure, uremia) Specify: 6. Cardiotoxic drug / other toxins. Specify: 7. Chest cavity radiation 8. Myocardial infarction 9. Pulmonary embolism 10. Mediastinitis 11. Other: Describe below like mediastinitis</p>

SPEAC INTERPRETATION FORM FOR MYOCARDITIS and PERICARDITIS CRITERION VALUES: * *These criteria are relevant only to the pericarditis case definition*

CRITERIA		CRITERION OPTIONS			Criterion Value
		Criterion = YES (Y) IF:	Criterion = NO (N) IF:	Criterion = UNKNOWN (U) IF:	
A-1: Cardiac Symptoms		≥1 of A-1: (1,2,3,4 or 5) OR A4-1	A-1 = 6	A-1 - 7	A-1 = Y N U
A-2: Non-specific symptoms: Relevant to Adult/older child		≥2 of A-2: (1,2,3,4 or 5) OR A4-1	< 2 of A-2(1,2,3,4 or 5) OR A2 = 12	A-2 = 13	A-2 = Y N U
A-3: Non-specific symptoms: Relevant to Infant/young child		≥2 of A-3: (1,2,3,4 or 5) OR A4-1	< 2 of A-3(1,2,3,4 or 5) OR A3 = 6	A-3 = 7	A-3 = Y N U
A-4: Combination of A-1 & A-2		≥1 of A-1(1-3) & ≥2 of A-2(3- 11) OR A4-2	A-1 = None of (1,2 or 3) OR A-2 = <2 of (3-11) OR A-2 = 12	A-1 = 7 or A-2 = 13	A-4 = Y N U
B: Physical exam features	B-1*	For B-1: ≥1 of B (1, 2 or 3)	B = 4	B = 5	B-1 = Y N U
	B-2*	For B-2: ≥1 of B: (1 +/-or 2)	B = 4	B = 5	B-2 = Y N U
C-Inflammatory markers		C = 1,2,3 or 4 OR C-6	C = 5	C = 0	C = Y N U
D-Cardiac biomarkers	D-1	D = 1 +/-or 2	D = 4	D = 0	D-1 = Y N U
	D-2	D = 3 OR D2-6	D = 5	D = 0	D-2 = Y N U
E-ECG (Electrocardiogram)	E-1	E = 1 +/-or 2 +/-or 3	E = 11	E = 0	E-1 = Y N U
	E-2	E = 4 +/-or 5 +/-or 6 OR E-7	E = 11	E = 0	E-2 = Y N U
	E-3*	E = all 3 of (7 + 8 + 9)	E = 11	E = 0	E-3 = Y N U
	E-4*	E = 1-2 of (7 or 8 or 9)	E = 11	E = 0	E-4 = Y N U
	E-5*	E = 10	E = 11	E = 0	E-5 = Y N U
F-Echocardiogram	F-1	F = ≥1 of:(1,2 3,4or5) OR F1-8	F = 7	F = 0	F-1 = Y N U
	F-2*	F = 6 OR F1-9	F = 7	F = 0	F-2 = Y N U

G-cMR (Cardiac Magnetic Resonance imaging)	G-1	<u>G = 1 +/or 2 OR G-6</u>	<u>G = 4</u>	<u>G = 0</u>	G-1 = Y N U
	G-2*	<u>G = 3 OR G-7</u>	<u>G = 4</u>	<u>G = 0</u>	G-2 = Y N U
H-Chest MRI/CT	H*	<u>H = 1 OR H-4</u>	<u>H = 2</u>	<u>H = 0</u>	H = Y N U
I-Chest-X-Ray	I*	<u>I = 1 OR I-4</u>	<u>I = 2</u>	<u>I = 0</u>	I = Y N U
J-Endomyocardial Biopsy (heart tissues microscopy)	J-1	<u>J = 1</u>	<u>J = 3</u>	<u>J = 0</u>	J-1 = Y N U
	J-2*	<u>J = 2</u>	<u>J = 3</u>	<u>J = 0</u>	J-2 = Y N U
X-Alternative diagnosis	X	Any of X (1-11) checked	No alternative diagnosis	Not Applicable	X = Y N

Level of Certainty	MYOCARDITIS
Level 1 : 2 possibilities (1.1 OR 1.2)	1.1 J-1 = YES
	1.2 [D-1 = YES) AND (F-1 OR G-1 = YES)]
Level 2A	[A-1 OR A-2 OR A-3 = YES] AND [(D1 +/-or D2 = YES) OR (E-1 = YES) OR (F-1 = YES) OR (G-1 = YES)] AND [X = NO]
Level 2B	A4-1=YES AND [D2-6=YES OR E-12=YES OR F-8=YES OR G-6=YES] AND [X = NO]
Level 3A	[A-1 OR A-2 OR A-3 = YES] AND [(C = YES) OR (E-2 = YES)] AND [X = NO]
Level 3B	A4-1=YES AND [C-6=YES] AND [X = NO]
Level 4A	Reported as a case of myocarditis by specialist but fails to meet any level of certainty AND [X = NO]
Level 4B	Reported as a case of myocarditis but fails to meet any level of certainty
Level 5	X = YES (NOTE : this exclusion applies only to levels 2 and 3)

Level of Certainty	PERICARDITIS
Level 1 : 2 possibilities (1.1 OR 1.2)	1.1 J-2 = YES
	1.2 ≥2 of : [(B-1 = YES) OR (E-3 = YES) OR (F-2 or G-2 or H = YES)]
Level 2A	[A-1 or A-3 = YES] AND [(B2 = YES) OR (E-4 = YES) OR (F-2 or G-2 or H = YES)] AND [X = NO]
Level 2B	A4-2=YES AND [D2-6=YES OR E-13=YES OR F-9=YES OR G-7=YES] AND [X = NO]
Level 3A	[A-3 or A-4 = YES] AND [(E-5 = YES) or (I = YES)] AND [X = NO]
Level 3B	A4-2*=YES AND [I-4=YES] AND [X = NO]
Level 4A	Reported as a case of pericarditis by specialist but fails to meet any level of certainty AND [X = NO]
Level 4B	Reported as a case of pericarditis but fails to meet any level of certainty
Level 5	X = YES (NOTE : this exclusion applies only to levels 2 and 3)

3. Thrombosis with thrombocytopenia syndrome (TTS)

The BC case definition for TTS used was :

Chen R, Buttery J. DRAFT - TTS: Case definition & guidelines for data collection, analysis, and presentation of immunization safety data. Zenodo; Nov 2021. DOI [10.5281/zenodo.6697332](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6697332).

The VAC4EU data collection form below was based on this, but included modifications (in green), to make criteria more explicit and to be more suitable for the reality of RWD. This form was built subsequently in REDCAP and automated logic was applied to calculate the LOCs.

The following changes are implemented to the original Brighton Collaboration form:

- Inclusion of additional symptoms for clinical syndromes to guide case abstraction.
- Acceptance of specialist-confirmed diagnoses without detailed supporting evidence for each syndrome to accommodate missing or incomplete documentation in RWD.
- Detailed D-dimer cutoffs, including age-adjusted thresholds and definitions for “ $\geq 8 \times$ ULN” to support standardised interpretation.
- Structured section to document differential diagnoses that could exclude TTS.
- Inclusion of Levels 4a and 4b to distinguish between cases reported by a specialist without sufficient evidence and those lacking both evidence and specialist confirmation.
- Retention of Level 5 for cases meeting exclusion criteria or not fulfilling LOC 1–3 requirements.
- Addition of checkboxes and explicit “Yes/No/Unknown” fields to enable automated LOC assignment.
- Integration of footnotes with laboratory reference ranges to guide consistent abstraction.

Table 2. TTS data abstraction form

1. Date of event onset	
2. Date of Thrombocytopenia	
3. Hospital admission? (no/yes, date)	
4. Admission diagnosis:	
5. Discharge diagnosis:	

The case definition (CD) level of certainty (LOC) were determined based on a series of clinical conditions defined below.

Condition A: Platelet count $<150 \times 10^9/L$ and of new onset with no known recent exposure to heparin (within the last 30 days), Platelet count value and unit _____

- Yes
- No
- Unknown

Condition B1: Presence of thrombosis/thromboembolism confirmed by ≥ 1 of the following (Check all that apply below)

Imaging Study

- Ultrasound – Doppler
- CT scan – contrast / angiography
- Magnetic resonance venography or arteriography
- Echocardiogram
- Perfusion V/Q scan
- Conventional angiography / digital subtraction angiography
- No imaging studies done, unknown if done, or done but results unknown
- The imaging done, but no sign of thrombosis is presents

Surgical procedure - that confirmed presence of a thrombus (e.g. thrombectomy)

Please describe: _____

Pathologic examination – including biopsy or autopsy

Please describe: _____

Condition B2: Severe and persistent headache around 10 days before or after onset of event with elevated D-dimer ≥ 4000 mcg/L (FEU) OR Elevated D-dimer $\geq 8x$ ULN for age ^a

The highest value: _____

Condition C: Clinical presentation suggests one of the specific clinical syndromes below? (Check the most appropriate) NOTE: The signs/symptoms for each criterion are suggestive of the syndrome if **any of them is present you can check the item**. Diagnosis of the syndrome by a clinical specialist is also acceptable

Cerebral venous sinus thrombosis / other cerebral venous thrombosis

- New onset of unexplained headache, often severe, typically persisting;
- Focal cerebral dysfunction
- Encephalopathy
- Seizure
- Blurred vision
- Double vision
- Loss of, or change in, level of consciousness;
- Ocular chemosis
- Confirmation by specialist without details
- Unknown

Deep vein thrombosis

- New onset swelling usually but not always in lower extremities;
- localised swelling accompanied by pain [may be crampy in nature] and tenderness
- Reddened/discoloured/warm skin
- Pitting edema;
- Absent pulses in legs or arms
- Calf pain or tenderness
- Confirmation by specialist without details
- Unknown

Pulmonary thromboembolism

- Sudden onset: shortness of breath [at rest or on exertion]
- Pleuritic chest pain [sudden, intense, sharp, stabbing or burning in nature, made worse by breathing/coughing/sneezing/laughing]
- Cough +/- hemoptysis

- Tachypnea
- Tachycardia
- Arrhythmia
- Cyanosis
- Hypotension
- Confirmation by specialist without details
- Unknown

Intra-abdominal thrombosis.

- Abdominal pain [may be out of proportion to physical exam findings],
- Bloating
- nausea
- Vomiting
- Diarrhea
- Bloody stools
- Ascites
- Hepatomegaly if hepatic vein location
- Confirmation by specialist without details
- Unknown

Ischemic stroke

- Sudden onset of focal neurologic deficits such as difficulty with speech [dysphasia or dysarthria]
- Hemiparesis
- Ataxic gait
- Abnormal eye movements
- Facial paresis
- Confirmation by specialist without details
- Unknown

Myocardial infarction

- Chest pain [often crushing in nature]
- Shortness of breath
- Arrhythmias
- Cyanosis
- Sudden death

- Confirmation by specialist without details
- Unknown

Arterial Thrombosis

- Pale colour of the arm or leg
- Cold arm or leg
- Decreased or no pulse in an arm or leg
- Lack of movement in the arm or leg
- Weakness of an arm or leg
- Confirmation by specialist without details
- Unknown

Condition D: One or more of these imaging or lab findings supportive of the diagnosis of thrombosis / thromboembolism? (Check all that apply)

- Echocardiogram or doppler ultrasound
 - Computed tomography without contrast or MRI
 - 2000 >D-dimer \geq 500 mcg/L (FEU) OR D-dimer (Elevated above upper limit of normal for age ^a)
- The highest value: _____

Condition E: At least one of these Lab findings that are strongly supportive of the diagnosis of platelet-activating antibody mediated thrombosis? (Check all that apply)

- 4000 >D-dimer \geq 2000 mcg/L (FEU) OR D-dimer (Elevated above 4 times upper limit of normal for age ^a)
- The highest value: _____
- Positive anti-platelet factor 4 (PF4) assay: specific anti-PF4 ELISA (note: rapid tests are insensitive for these antibodies) or functional test with addition of PF4
 - Yes
 - No
 - Unknown

Condition F: Reported as a case of TTS by specialist, without details

- Yes
- No

Condition X: Alternative diagnosis

- Yes, An alternative diagnosis was found that explained the acute illness, describe:
- No, No alternative diagnosis was found to explain the acute illness

Level of Certainty for TTS

If yes to (A and B1) is level 1

yes to (A and B2) and X = NO: then is Level 1

If no to (B1 and B2)_and_[If yes to A plus yes to (C and E)] and X=NO then is level 1

If no to (B1 and B2)_and_NO to X and [If yes to A plus yes to (C and D)] then is level 2

If no to (B1 and B2)_and_NO to X and _[If yes to A plus [(yes to C) and (no to D and E)] then is level 3

If there is insufficient information to determine the conditions needed to a level of certainty of 1, 2 or 3 and F = Yes then the level of certainty is level 4a

If there is insufficient information to determine the conditions needed to a level of certainty of 1, 2 or 3 and F = No then the level of certainty is level 4b

If there is sufficient information to determine the conditions A, B, C, D, and E but the aggregate of the conditions do not meet the LOC 1, 2, or 3 then the LOC is Level 5; Not a Case of TTS and/or X = Yes

^aAge-adjusted D-dimer

D-dimer levels rise with age such that using the traditional cutoff value of < 500 ng/mL (fibrinogen equivalent units) results in reduced specificity of D-dimer testing in older patients (>50 years), a population in whom PE is common. Several studies report its use with the most commonly used formula for age adjustment as:

Age (if over 50 years) x 10 = cutoff value in ng/mL or ug/L (fibrinogen equivalent units)

If reported by the lab as a D-dimer unit (DDU) the cutoff is often **230 ng/mL**.

2 FEUs equal 1 DDU.

- If using a lab with a cutoff of 230 (DDU assay) then formula is Age x 5

1. **Example 1-A: 45-year-old** patient was admitted to the hospital with **D-dimer 300 ng/mL**: since the patient is <50 years old the traditional standard cutoff value of 500 ng/mL should be applied. We can see that the **D-dimer value is below the threshold**. (300 ng/mL < 500 ng/mL)
2. **Example 2-A: 65-year-old** man was admitted to hospital with **D-dimer 600 ng/mL**.as the patient is >50 years old the age-adjusted formula is applied and the age (65) is multiplied by 10, resulting in a cutoff value of 650 ng/mL. **The patient's D-dimer level (600 ng/mL), is below the threshold**(for this patient, 8x ULN would be 650 x 8).

4. Guillain-Barré syndrome (GBS)

The BC case definition for GBS used was :

Law B, Dekker CL, Sturkenboom, M. AESI Case Definition Companion Guide: Guillain Barré and Miller Fisher Syndrome; Feb 2021. DOI [10.5281/zenodo.6668878](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6668878).

The VAC4EU data collection form below was based on this and modifications were made (in green), to make criteria more explicit and to adapt to the reality of RWD. This form was built subsequently in REDCAP and automated logic was applied to attribute the LOC.

The following changes were made to the original BC data collection form:

- Level 4 divided into level 4a and level 4b :
 - Level 4a for cases insufficient for LOC 1–3 but confirmed by a specialist (Criterion G = Yes).
 - Level 4b for cases insufficient for LOC 1–3 and not confirmed by a specialist.
- Introduced standard “Yes/No/Unknown” fields for all criteria to enable automated LOC assignment in REDCap.

Table 3. GBS data abstraction form

1. Record specific information, to the extent possible, for all column 1 criteria in the results column 2 below.
2. Use recorded results to circle most appropriate BCCD criterion value based on the formulae in column 3.

Clinical criteria	Results				3. BCCD criteria value determination	
Criteria A & B Flaccid (reduced tone) weakness (graded power of 4 or less – see Table 5 below)	* Wherever ‘yes’ is chosen, indicate the worst grade of muscle strength during course (See Table 5. Assessment of Muscle Strength)				A=A-1 (bilateral flaccid paralysis) IF: Both legs and/or both arms are weak or have a quantitative muscle strength <5 A=A-2 (absence of weakness) IF: Both legs & both arms have normal muscle strength or graded strength = 5 Else A = Not met if neither A-1 nor A-2 B = B-1 IF Deep tendon reflexes are absent or decreased in weak limbs (essential for GBS) ^{1,2} B = B-2 IF absent or reduced tendon reflexes in both legs and/or both arms despite absence of weakness Else B = Not met if neither B-1 nor B-2	
	R = right; L = left	1. R leg	2. L leg	3. R arm		4. L arm
	A-1. Qualitative muscle strength: N =normal; W =weak; Unknown = not done, or unknown if done, or done but unknown in results					
	A-2. Quantitative muscle strength (0-5): Lowest recorded score if available					
B. Deep tendon reflexes: A =absent; D =decreased; N =normal; I =increased; Unknown = not done, or unknown if done, or done but unknown in results Leg: Kn =knee; Ank =ankle Arm: Bi =biceps; Tri =triceps;						

Clinical criteria	Results	3. BCCD criteria value determination
<p>Criterion C Monophasic temporal illness pattern²</p>	<p>a) Is weakness onset date available ? Yes* _No Not documented *if Yes, provide details: (dd/mm/yy): / / _</p> <p>b) Is Date when weakness at its worst (nadir) available: Yes* _No Not documented *if Yes, provide details: (dd/mm/yy): / / [if (a) and (b) are Yes then option (c) will be displayed. Otherwise, the interval between (a) and (b) is unknown]</p> <p>c) Interval between (a) and (b) : _____ Hrs* OR _____ Days OR _____ * if same day record the interval in Hrs</p> <p>d) Date of last observation: (dd/mm/yy): / ____ / ____ _ unknown</p> <p>e) Clinical status at the last observation: _____ complete recovery to baseline status _____ partial recovery but still has some residual weakness / disability _____ no change in weakness from the nadir _____ dead</p> <p>f) Fluctuation in degree of weakness between: 1. onset and nadir*: __Yes __No Not documented 2. nadir and last observation: __Yes __No Not documented If 'Yes' for f-1 and/or f-2, were the fluctuations associated with disease modifying therapies (e.g. IVIG, steroids)? __Yes* No not described * if Yes, provide details:</p>	<p>C = YES IF: interval from onset to weakness nadir is between 12 hrs and 28 days</p> <p>C = NO IF: interval from onset to weakness nadir is <12 hours OR >28 days</p> <p>C = UNKNOWN IF: unable to calculate a value for interval from onset to weakness nadir</p>
<p>Criterion D Ophthalmoparesis</p>	<p>a) R extraocular muscle weakness: __Yes __No __Not described</p> <p>b) L extraocular muscle weakness: __Yes __No __Not described</p>	<p>D = Present IF yes for both R & L D = Absent IF No for both R & L D = UNKNOWN IF not described for R+ / or L</p>
<p>Criterion E Ataxia</p>	<p>Ataxia _Present Absent __Not described</p>	<p>E = Present or Absent if either is checked OR = UNKNOWN IF Not described checked</p>

Clinical criteria	Results	3. BCCD criteria value determination
Criterion F. Altered level of consciousness	Reduction or alteration of level of consciousness: _____ Present _____ Absent _____ Not described	F = Present or Absent if either is checked F = Unknown IF Not described checked
Criterion G Corticospinal tract signs	Corticospinal tract signs were: Present Absent _Not described, e.g., extensor plantar responses, spasticity, Increased muscle tone	G = Present or Absent if either is checked G = Unknown IF Not described is checked
Criterion H Alternative cause for weakness found ³	Complete Table 6 checklist as completely as possible and then choose the best choice for the statement: An identified alternative Diagnosis for weakness was: Present* Absent (check if no testing done) *Describe alternative cause and basis for diagnosis:	H = circle whatever is checked Present Absent

Laboratory criteria	Results	
Criterion I Electro-physiologic findings ⁴	Neurophysiologic testing: DONE* Not Done Unknown if Done or Results unavailable *If DONE check the result that is most consistent with the report a. _Acute Inflammatory Demyelinating Polyneuropathy (AIDP) b. _Acute Motor Axonal Neuropathy (AMAN) c. Acute Motor and Sensory Axonal Neuropathy (AMSAN) d. _Sensory abnormalities only e. _Inexcitable or unknown pattern f. normal result g. other (describe):	I = I-1 "Typical for GBS" IF a (AIDP) OR b (AMAN) or c (AMSAN) checked I = I-2 if d (sensory only) or f (normal) checked I = I-3 if testing Not done OR unknown if done OR results unavailable OR Done and e checked (inexcitable / unknown pattern). NOTE: If g(other) checked, seek expert help for interpretation.

Laboratory criteria	Results	
<p>Criterion J Lumbar puncture (LP) and CSF exam</p>	<p>Lumbar Puncture: DONE* Not done Unknown if Done * If DONE: Date (dd / mon / yy) / ___ /)</p> <p>CSF protein ⁵ (mg/L if known _____): Normal Elevated Unknown</p> <p>CSF total WBC count: _____ <50 / uL ≥50/uL Unknown (actual count in cells/uL if known ____):</p>	<p>J = J-1 'cytoalbuminologic dissociation' IF CSF WBC < 50/uL and CSF protein elevated</p> <p>J = J-2 IF CSF WBC <50/uL and CSF protein normal or result unknown</p> <p>J = J-3 IF LP not done or done but CSF results unavailable or ≥ 50/uL</p>
<p>Criterion K (Neurologist, Internist)</p>	<p>1) Reported as a case of GBS by specialist, without details <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p>2) Reported as a case of MF by specialist, without details <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>	

¹ For GBS absent/decreased DTRs must be demonstrated in the same limbs that are weak to meet the case definition; having absent/decreased DTRs in unaffected limbs does not impact the case definition.

² Decreased/absent deep tendon reflex in non homologous muscles would be considered as bilateral and met B1

² Monophasic illness patterns: "fluctuations in level of weakness, before reaching nadir, or during the plateau or improvement phases, occur in some cases, usually associated with use of disease-modifying therapies (steroids, IVIG, plasma exchange). Such fluctuations usually occur within the first 9 weeks after onset and are followed by eventual improvement"

³ Testing for alternate causes of weakness is not required to meet the case definition; but IF FOUND, then not a case.

⁴ Tests may be normal if done sooner than 7 days after weakness onset; in such cases should be repeated.

⁵ The normal CSF protein concentration ranges from 23 to 38 mg/dL (0.23 to 0.38 g/L) in adults³

³ Hasbun R. Cerebrospinal fluid in central nervous system infections. In: Infections of the central nervous system, 4th edition, Scheld WM, Whitley RJ, Marra CM (Eds), Lippincott Williams, 2014. p.4.

Use answers in data abstraction form and formulae below to determine level of certainty for GBS (4A) or Miller Fisher syndrome (4B) :

Level of Certainty	4A. GBS
Level 1	[A = A1] & [B = B1] & [C=YES] AND [H = Absent] AND [I = I-1] AND [J = J-1]
Level 2	[A = A1] & [B = B1] & [C=YES] AND [H = Absent] EITHER i. [I = I-1] AND [J = J-2 or J-3] OR ii. [I = I-3] AND [J = J-2]
Level 3	[A = A1] & [B = B1] & [C=YES] AND [H = Absent] AND [I = I-3] AND [J = J-3]
Level 4a	Reported as GBS but Insufficient information available to meet any level of case definition and K1= Yes
Level 4b	Reported as GBS but Insufficient information available to meet any level of case definition and K1= No
Level 5	Not a case: [NO to A1, B1 or C] AND/OR [H = Present]

* if limb weakness (A = 1) is present the illness may be GBS/Miller Fisher overlap syndrome. If so, apply the criteria for GBS to determine level of diagnostic certainty.

Level of Certainty	4B. Miller Fisher syndrome*
Level1	[A=A2] & [B = B2] & [C =YES] & [D&E]=Present & ([F & G & H]=Absent) & [I = I-2] & [J = J1]
Level2	[A=A2] & [B = B2] & [C =YES OR UNKNOWN] & [D&E]=Present & ([F & G & H]= Absent) AND EITHER i. [I = I-2] AND [J = J-2 or J-3] OR ii. [I = I-3] AND [J = J-2]
Level3	[A=A2] & [B = B2] & [C =YES OR UNKNOWN] & [D&E]=Present & ([F & G & H]= Absent) AND [I = I-3] AND [J = J-3]
Level 4a	Reported as Miller Fisher Syndrome but insufficient information available to meet any level of case definition and K2=Yes
Level 4b	Reported as Miller Fisher but Insufficient information available to meet any level of case definition and K2= No
Level5	Not a case : [NO to any of [A] AND [B-2 OR C] or Absent for [D or E] OR [Present for any of [F, G or H]

Criteria for Assessment of severity of weakness at clinical nadir and follow-up for outcome

Medical Research Council Manual Muscle Testing Scale

Grade	Muscular capability
0	No contractile activity
1	Muscle activity can be palpated when performing action, with gravity eliminated
2	Patient can move limb with gravity eliminated through partial range of motion
3	Patient can't hold against resistance, but is able to move limb against gravity through range of motion
4	Patient can hold the position against moderate resistance, has full range of motion
5	Patient can hold the position against maximal resistance and through complete range of motion

Investigation(s) for alternative diagnoses for weakness: for any 'yes' answers: provide detail.

Nervous system level	Investigated?	Alternative explanation for weakness	Present
Intracranial		Encephalitis, ADEM	Yes No Unknown
		Carcinomatous meningitis	Yes No Unknown
		Brain stem stroke or encephalitis (Bickerstaff's)	Yes No Unknown
		Wernicke's encephalopathy (thiamine deficiency)	Yes No Unknown
Spinal cord			Yes No Unknown
		Infarct Myelitis Compression	Yes No Unknown
			Yes No Unknown
Anterior horn cells of spinal cord		Viral infection: Polio / VAPP, West Nile Virus, Zika Virus Amyotrophic	Yes No Unknown
		lateral sclerosis	Yes No Unknown
		Progressive spinal muscular atrophy	Yes No Unknown
Spinal nerve roots		Chronic inflammatory demyelinating polyneuropathy (CIDP) Cauda	Yes No Unknown
		equina compression	Yes No Unknown

Nervous system level	Investigated?	Alternative explanation for weakness	Present
Peripheral nerves			Yes No Unknown
			Yes No Unknown
		Metabolic derangements (magnesium, phosphates etc.) Tick paralysis	Yes No Unknown
		Heavy metal toxicity (arsenic, gold or thallium)	Yes No Unknown
		Drug-induced neuropathy (vincristine, platinum, nitrofurantoin, paclitaxel) Porphyria	Yes No Unknown
		Critical illness neuropathy vasculitis	Yes No Unknown
		Diphtheria, Lyme disease, thiamine deficiency	Yes No Unknown
			Yes No Unknown
Neuromuscular junction			Yes No Unknown
		Myasthenia gravis Organophosphate poisoning Botulism	Yes No Unknown
			Yes No Unknown
Muscle			Yes No Unknown
			Yes No Unknown
		Critical illness myopathy, polymyositis dermatomyositis	Yes No Unknown
		Hypo / hyperkalemia, rhabdomyolysis, mitochondrial disease	Yes No Unknown
			Yes No Unknown

5. Anaphylaxis

The BC case definition for anaphylaxis used was

Law B, Huang, WT, Sturkenboom, M. AESI Case Definition Companion Guide: Anaphylaxis Version 2. Zenodo; Oct 2022. DOI [10.5281/zenodo.6668844](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6668844).

The VAC4EU data extraction form below was based on this, but included changes (in green), to make criteria more explicit and more adapted to the reality of RWD. This form was built in REDCAP subsequently and automated logic was applied to calculate the LOC.

The following changes were implemented to the original Brighton Collaboration form:

- Added Criterion G for 'Reported as a case of anaphylaxis by a specialist, without details' (e.g., immunologist, emergency medicine physician, internist) to allow classification in cases where documentation in RWD is incomplete.
- Standardised "Yes/No/Unknown" options for all criteria to support automated logic execution in REDCap.
- Structured field to document whether an alternative diagnosis was found, with requirement to describe the alternative condition when present.
- Level 4 divided into Level 4a and Level 4b
 - Level 4a for cases insufficient for LOC 1–3 but confirmed by a specialist (Criterion G = Yes).
 - Level 4b for cases insufficient for LOC 1–3 and not confirmed by a specialist.

Table 4. Anaphylaxis data abstraction form

Record date and time of onset of the first symptom or sign of anaphylaxis:		
1. Criterion A. Rapid progression of symptoms and signs	i. Read this statement carefully: From the start of symptoms or signs of possible anaphylaxis, there were multiple body systems involved (≥ 2 of skin, respiratory, cardiovascular or gastrointestinal) OR what started out involving 1 system spread to involve at least 1 other system within 1 hour of onset.	ii. Statement 'i' is (choose the one best answer): <input type="checkbox"/> 1. True <input type="checkbox"/> 2. False <input type="checkbox"/> 3. Unable to confirm as either true or false
2. Criteria B. Skin symptoms or signs	Check all that were present of 1,2,3,4 or 5, OR choose only 6 or 7 depending on which is most accurate	<input type="checkbox"/> 1. Urticaria (hives) at a location other than the vaccine administration site <input type="checkbox"/> 2. Angioedema (skin swelling) at a location other than the vaccine administration site <input type="checkbox"/> 3. Generalised (widespread) erythema (redness) of the skin WITH pruritis (itchiness of the skin) <input type="checkbox"/> 4. Generalised (widespread) erythema (redness) of the skin
3. Criteria C Cardiac symptoms or signs	Check one or both of 1 or 2 if present; OR choose either 3 or 4 depending on which is most accurate.	<input type="checkbox"/> 1. Hypotension <input type="checkbox"/> 2. Loss of consciousness <input type="checkbox"/> 3. Neither 1 nor 2 were present <input type="checkbox"/> 4. Unknown if 1 or 2 were present

<p>4. Criteria D. Respiratory symptoms or signs</p>	<p>D-1 Check all that were present of 1, 2, 3 and 4; OR choose either 5 or 6 depending on which is most accurate.</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> 1. Expiratory wheeze (when breathing out) documented by a healthcare professional, with or without a stethoscope</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 2. Inspiratory stridor (when breathing in) documented by a healthcare professional, with or without a stethoscope</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 3. Upper airways swelling of the tongue, pharynx (throat), uvula or larynx - unequivocally documented by a healthcare professional. <i>Note: isolated lip swelling, if present, is angioedema (see B2 above) not upper airway swelling</i></p>
	<p>D-2 Check all that were present of 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6; OR choose either 7 or 8 depending on which is most accurate.</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> 1. Tachypnoea</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 2. Cyanosis</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 3. Grunting</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 4. Chest wall retractions</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 5. Increased use of accessory respiratory muscles</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 6. Measured hypoxia: oxygen saturation <90%</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 7. None of 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 or 6 presents</p>
<p>5. Criterion E Gastrointestinal symptoms</p>	<p>Check one or both of 1, 2 if present; OR choose either 3 or 4 depending on which is most accurate. NOTE: these count towards anaphylaxis, ONLY in the context of an intranasally administered or injected vaccine. They are not relevant for oral vaccines.</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> 1 New onset vomiting (at least 2 episodes in infants <12 months of age)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 2 New onset diarrhoea (at least 2 episodes in infants < 12 months of age)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 3. Neither 1 nor 2 were present</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 4. Unknown if 1 or 2 were present</p>

<p>6. Criterion F Mast cell tryptase</p>	<p>Check best option</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> 1 Mast cell tryptase > upper limit of normal for lab doing test OR 1.2 times baseline measurement + 2ng/L</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 2 Mast cell tryptase not elevated, or not tested, or unknown if tested or results not available</p>
<p>7. Criterion G Case reported (immunologist, emergency medicine physician, internist)</p>	<p>Check best option</p>	<p>Reported as a case of anaphylaxis by the specialist, without details</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 1. Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 2. No</p>
<p>8. Criterion X Alternative diagnosis</p>	<p>Check best option</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> 1 Yes, an alternative diagnosis was found that explained the acute illness, describe:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 2 No, no alternative diagnosis was found to explain the acute illness</p>

INTERPRETATION FORM FOR ANAPHYLAXIS CRITERION VALUES: Based on clinical data entered into data abstraction form, assign a value to each criterion using the rules in the options for criterion value columns.

CRITERIA		Options for criterion value			Criterion Value
		YES (Y) IF:	NO (N) IF:	UNKNOWN (U) IF:	
Criterion A	Rapid	<u> </u> A = 1	<u> </u> A = 2	<u> </u> A = 3	A = Y
Criterion B	Major B-1	<u> </u> B = 1 or 2 or 3	<u> </u> B = 4 or 5 or 6 AND B	<u> </u> B = 7	B-1 = Y
	Minor B-2	<u> </u> B = 4 or 5	<u> </u> B = 1 or 2 or 3 or 6 AND	<u> </u> B = 7	B-2 = Y
Criterion C	Cardiac Major:	<u> </u> C = 1 or 2	<u> </u> C = 3	<u> </u> C = 4	C = Y N
Criterion D	Major D-1	<u> </u> D-1 = (1 or 2 or 3) OR <u> </u> D-2 = ≥2 of (1, 2, 3, 4, 5 or 6)	<u> </u> D-1 = 5 AND D-2 = 7 OR <u> </u> D-1 = 5 AND D-2 = ≤1 of (1,2,3,4,5or6)	<u> </u> D-1 = 6 & D-2 = 8	D-1 = Y N U
	Minor D-3	<u> </u> D-1 = 4	<u> </u> D-1 ne 4 OR D-1 = 5	<u> </u> D-1 = 6	D-2 = Y N U
Criterion E	GI Major:	<u> </u> E = 1 or 2	<u> </u> E = 3	<u> </u> E = 4	E = Y N
Criterion F	Laboratory	<u> </u> F = 1	Not applicable	<u> </u> F = 2	F = Y
Criterion G	Case reported	<u> </u> G = 1	<u> </u> G = 2	Not applicable	G = Y N
Criterion X	Alternative	<u> </u> X = 1	<u> </u> X = 2	Not applicable	X = Y

Tabular algorithm to determine anaphylaxis v-2 level of certainty (LOC) based on criterion values

Level of certainty	Anaphylaxis V-2
Level 1	A = Yes AND B-1 = Yes AND ≥ 1 OF (C or D-1 or E or F) = Yes
Level 2	A = Yes AND B-1 = (No or Unknown) AND ≥ 2 of (C or D-1 or E or F) = Yes AND X=No
Level 3	A = Yes AND B-1 = (No OR Unknown) AND X=No AND either of the following : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o 1 of (D-1) = Yes AND (B-2) = Yes o 1 of (C or E or F) = Yes AND (B-2 or D-2) = Yes
Level 4a	Unable to meet any level of certainty (1, 2 or 3) because of insufficient information AND G=1
Level 4b	Unable to meet any level of certainty (1, 2 or 3) because of insufficient information
Level 5	A = No OR only a single system is involved (B or C or D or E or F) AND/OR X=Yes

6. Idiopathic thrombocytopenia (ITP)

The BC case definition for ITP used was :

Law B, Huang WT, Sturkenboom M. AESI Case Definition Companion Guide: Thrombocytopenia. Zenodo; Feb 2021. DOI 10.5281/zenodo.6668864

The VAC4EU form below has built on this with modifications (in green), to make criteria more explicit and to be adapted for the reality of RWD. This form was subsequently built in REDCAP and automated logic was applied to calculate LOC

The following changes are implemented to the original Brighton Collaboration form:

- Included Criterion E for 'Reported as a case of ITP by a specialist, without details' to classify cases with incomplete clinical or laboratory information in RWD.
- Clear specification of platelet count thresholds ($<150 \times 10^9/L$)
- Inclusion of specific diagnostic evidence:
 - bone marrow cytology/histology findings
 - anti-platelet antibody positivity
 - high serum cytokine levels and/or abnormal liver function tests
 - medication history relevant to thrombocytopenia
 - surgical/pathological findings supporting the diagnosis
- Clear "Yes/No" fields for each criterion to enable automated LOC assignment in REDCap.
- Added Levels 4A and 4B to differentiate between specialist-confirmed cases without sufficient evidence and cases lacking sufficient evidence but not confirmed by a specialist.

Table 5. Idiopathic thrombocytopenia data abstraction form

1.Date of Thrombocytopenia	
2. Hospital admission? (no/yes, date_)	
3. Admitting diagnosis:	
4. Discharge diagnosis:	
A-Decreased platelet count	<input type="checkbox"/> 1. count <150X10 ⁹ /L <input type="checkbox"/> 2. count ≥ 150X10 ⁹ /L <input type="checkbox"/> 3. no count done OR results unknown How was the platelet count done: <input type="checkbox"/> not recorded <input type="checkbox"/> automated hematology analyser <input type="checkbox"/> cell count slide <input type="checkbox"/> Other. Describe _____ Lowest recorded platelet count X 10 ⁹ / L: _____
B - Peripheral blood smear	<input type="checkbox"/> 1.reduced platelet numbers with no clumping seen <input type="checkbox"/> 2. normal platelet numbers or clumping seen <input type="checkbox"/> 3. smear not done or results unavailable

<p>C- Clinical symptoms or signs indicating spontaneous bleeding</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> C1. ≥ 1 the below symptom/sign confirmed to be present.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Purpura <input type="checkbox"/> Petechia <input type="checkbox"/> Bruising <input type="checkbox"/> Hematoma <input type="checkbox"/> Epistaxis <input type="checkbox"/> Hematuria <input type="checkbox"/> Hematemesis <input type="checkbox"/> Hematochezia <input type="checkbox"/> Occult rectal bleeding <input type="checkbox"/> Hemorrhagic oozing of skin lesion <input type="checkbox"/> Conjunctival bleeding <input type="checkbox"/> Intracranial bleeding <input type="checkbox"/> Vaginal bleeding (unless menstruation) <p><input type="checkbox"/> C2. No clinical evidence of spontaneous bleeding</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> C3. No documentation of any symptoms/signs of spontaneous bleeding</p>
<p>D-Laboratory examination</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> D1. ≥ 1 the below confirmed the causality of event.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Bone marrow cytology and histology: please describe (A shift to young, immature, less polyploid megakaryocytes and fewer mature megakaryocytes) 2. Anti-platelet antibodies positive 3. High serum cytokine levels AND/OR abnormal liver function tests 4. Medication history: e.g. heparin, warfarin, rituximab, clopidogrel, ticlopidine, chemotherapy medications. 5. Surgical and/or pathological findings and diagnoses: please describe <p><input type="checkbox"/> D2. No examination done, unknown if done, or done but results unknown</p>
<p>E-Specialist diagnosis (hematologist, internist)</p>	<p>Reported as a case of Idiopathic thrombocytopenia by specialist, without details</p> <p>Yes</p> <p>No</p>

<p>1</p>	<p>A1= YES AND [B1 OR C1 = YES] AND D1= NO</p>
<p>2</p>	<p>A1 = YES AND [B2 or B3] AND [C2 or C3] AND D1= NO AND level5 = NO</p>

3	Not applicable
4-A	E=YES AND level 5 = NO
4-B	Reported thrombocytopenia with insufficient evidence to meet the case definition AND/OR D2 = YES AND level 5 = NO
5	A2 AND/OR D1= YES AND level1 = NO

7. Transverse myelitis

The BC case definition for transverse myelitis used was

Law B, Chen R, Huang WT. AESI Case Definition Companion Guide: Myelitis. Zenodo; Feb 2021. DOI [10.5281/zenodo.6668654](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6668654).

The VAC4EU data collection form below was based on this with modifications (in green), to make criteria more explicit and to adapt for the reality of RWD. This form was subsequently built in REDCAP and automated logic was applied to calculate LOC.

The following changes were implemented to the original Brighton Collaboration form:

- Inclusion of a criterion for 'Reported case of transverse myelitis by a specialist without details' to classify cases with incomplete documentation.
- Standardised 'Yes/No/Unknown' responses for all criteria to support automated LOC assignment in REDCap.
- LOC sublevels (4A, 4B) to distinguish between insufficient evidence with and without specialist confirmation
- Added '**both sides of one section of the spinal cord**' to criterion A3, E5 and F2— this phrasing was added to improve precision of the definition and ensure consistent interpretation — versus other abnormalities.

Table 6. Transverse myelitis data abstraction form

<p>A3. Spinal cord histopathology</p>	<p>Spinal cord biopsy results: check all that apply below</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> 1-acute inflammation of both sides of one section of the spinal cord <input type="checkbox"/> 2-meningeal involvement in the inflammation <input type="checkbox"/> 3_normal histopathology <input type="checkbox"/> 4_Other- describe: <input type="checkbox"/> 5-Biopsy not done OR biopsy done results unknown OR unknown if Biopsy done 	
<p>D. Spinal cord symptoms / signs</p>	<p>D1 Limb weakness with upper motor neuron damage</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes (check all that apply below) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased muscle tone • spasticity • muscle rigidity • hyperreflexia • Other-describe <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Not tested <input type="checkbox"/> Unknown
	<p>D2 Limb weakness with evidence for lower motor neuron damage present</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes(check all that apply below) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decreased muscle tone • Flaccid paralysis / weakness • Decreased or absent deep tendon Reflexes • Fasciculations • Muscle atrophy • Other-describe <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Not tested <input type="checkbox"/> Unknown
	<p>D3 Sensory level</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Yes (indicate level if able) _____ <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Not tested <input type="checkbox"/> Unknown

	<p>D4 Autonomic dysfunction (can be any 1 of a, b or c)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> a. Bowel dysfunction: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Yes-describe below <input type="radio"/> No <input type="radio"/> Unknown <input type="checkbox"/> b. Bladder dysfunction: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Yes-describe below <input type="radio"/> No <input type="radio"/> Unknown <input type="checkbox"/> c. Erectile dysfunction: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> Yes-describe below <input type="radio"/> No <input type="radio"/> Unknown
--	--	--

Spine neuroimaging caveat: If both spine CT and MRI were done and the results differ, seek expert help to decide which most accurately reflects presence or absence of inflammation and/or demyelination consistent with myelitis.

Neuroimaging: Check best option for E5 & F2; if >1 examination, record most abnormal result; use extra pages to record other test dates and results, if applicable

E. Indicators of CNS inflammation	E1.Fever	<input type="checkbox"/> Fever temperature $\geq 38.0C$ by any measured method (history of fever is insufficient) highest temp: ____ <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Unknown																												
	E2.CSF	<input type="checkbox"/> Collected – Provide results below (sample date dd/mm/yy: _ / _ / _) <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="width: 40%;">CSF parameter</th> <th style="width: 40%;">Result</th> <th style="width: 20%;">Not tested or no result</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Opening/closing pressure(mmHg)</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>White blood cell count (cells/μL)</td> <td> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%;"> If age <2months •Yes If >15 WBC/μL •No If ≤ 15 WBC/μL </td> <td style="width: 50%;"> If age >2months •Yes if >5 WBC/μL No if ≤ 5 WBC/μL </td> </tr> </table> </td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>RBC count (cells/μL)</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Protein (mg/dL)</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Glucose (mg/dL)</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Gram stain</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Rapid antigen test</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Culture, other (describe):</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <input type="checkbox"/> Not collected <input type="checkbox"/> Unknown (culture other (describe))	CSF parameter	Result	Not tested or no result	Opening/closing pressure(mmHg)			White blood cell count (cells/ μ L)	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%;"> If age <2months •Yes If >15 WBC/μL •No If ≤ 15 WBC/μL </td> <td style="width: 50%;"> If age >2months •Yes if >5 WBC/μL No if ≤ 5 WBC/μL </td> </tr> </table>	If age <2months •Yes If >15 WBC/ μ L •No If ≤ 15 WBC/ μ L	If age >2months •Yes if >5 WBC/ μ L No if ≤ 5 WBC/ μ L		RBC count (cells/ μ L)			Protein (mg/dL)			Glucose (mg/dL)			Gram stain			Rapid antigen test			Culture, other (describe):	
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Glucose (mg/dL)																														
Gram stain																														
Rapid antigen test																														
Culture, other (describe):																														
Neuroimaging	E5.Spinal CT	<input type="checkbox"/> 0. Not done or done but results unavailable or unknown if done <input type="checkbox"/> 1. Evidence of acute inflammation of both side of one section of the spinal cord <input type="checkbox"/> 2. Normal <input type="checkbox"/> 3. Not normal but no evidence of acute inflammation of both side of one section of the spinal cord <input type="checkbox"/> 4. Other (Describe)																												

	F2.Spinal MRI	<input type="checkbox"/> 0. Not done or done but results unavailable or unknown if done <input type="checkbox"/> Evidence of acute inflammation of both side of one section of the spinal cord <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> 2. Normal <input type="checkbox"/> 3. Not normal but no evidence of acute inflammation of both side of one section of the spinal cord <input type="checkbox"/> 4. Other (Describe)
--	---------------	--

G. Specialist diagnosis (neurologist, infectious disease specialist, immunologist, internist)	Reported case of transverse myelitis by specialist but without details
X1.Exclusion criterion	Alternative diagnosis for illness <input type="checkbox"/> Yes *If yes describe, e.g. neoplasm, vascular disorder, infection, toxic/metabolic encephalopathy <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Unknown

Level 1	A3 = 1
Level 2	D = YES (IF ≥ 1 of (D1, D2, D3 or D4)) AND E ≥2 AND X1 = NOT MET
Level 3-A	D = YES AND E = 1 AND X1 = NOT MET
Level3-B	
Level 4-A	Reported case of acute myelitis with insufficient evidence to meet the case definition And G=YES
Level4-B	Reported case of acute myelitis with insufficient evidence to meet the case definition
Level 5 (Not a case)	D = NO AND/OR E = 0 AND/OR X1 = MET

Total indicators of CNS inflammation:

E = 0 : if NO / UNKNOWN for E1 + E2 + E5 + F21: if YES for only 1 of [E1 or E2 or E5 or F2] **≥2**: if YES for **≥2** of [E1 or E2 or E5 or F2]

8. Major congenital anomalies

The BC case definition for major congenital anomalies used was:

DeSilva M, Munoz FM, Mcmillan M, Kawai AT, Marshall H, Macartney KK, Joshi J, Oneko M, Rose AE, Dolk H, Trotta F, Spiegel H, Tomczyk S, Shrestha A, Kochhar S, Kharbanda EO; Brighton Collaboration Congenital Anomalies Working Group. Congenital anomalies: Case definition and guidelines for data collection, analysis, and presentation of immunization safety data. *Vaccine*. 2016;34(49):6015-6026. doi: 10.1016/j.vaccine.2016.03.047.

The Brighton Collaboration case definition was reformatted into **three separate forms** to improve clarity and facilitate structured data abstraction using RWD:

- Major major external structural congenital anomalies form
- Major major internal structural congenital anomalies form
- Major major functional congenital anomalies form

Table 7. Major major external structural congenital anomalies data abstraction form

Was the case tagged with major external structural congenital anomalies?

- Yes, then answer the following question and use sheet 1
- No

If yes, please select at least one of the items listed below :

Stillbirths	
Conjoined twins	
Central nervous system anomalies	
Neural tube defects	
Anencephalus & similar anomalies	
Spina bifida	
Encephalocele	
Microcephalus & brain reduction	
Congenital hydrocephalus	
Craniorachischisis	
Iniencephaly	
Other specified & unspecified CNS anomalies	Please describe
Holoprosencephaly	
Eye anomalies	
Anophthalmos, microphthalmos	

Congenital cataract	
Congenital glaucoma	
Other eye anomalies	Please describe
Ear face & neck anomalies	
Anotia/microtia	
Anomalies of ear causing impairment	
Other ear anomalies	Please describe
Anomalies of face & neck	
Respiratory system anomalies	
Nose anomalies	
Other respiratory system anomalies	Please describe
Choanal atresia	
Cleft lip and palate	
Cleft palate alone (without cleft lip)	
Cleft lip alone (without cleft palate)	
Cleft palate with cleft lip	
Genital organ anomalies	
Hypospadias, epispadias	
Indeterminate sex	
Other genital organ anomalies	Please describe
Urinary system anomalies	
Bladder exstrophy	
Cloacal exstrophy	
Other urinary system anomalies	Please describe
Musculoskeletal anomalies	
Certain musculoskeletal anomalies	
Clubfoot (talipes equinovarus)	

Polydactyly, syndactyly	
Craniosynostosis	
Gastroschisis	
Omphalocele	
Exomphalos	
Limb reduction anomalies	
Skeletal dysplasia	
Congenital absence of finger(s)	
Other, unspecified limb anomalies	Please describe
Congenital constriction bands/amniotic band	
Anomalies of abdominal wall	
Other musculoskeletal anomalies	Please describe
Anomalies of integument	
Other selected	Please describe
Congenital syphilis syndrome	
Congenital rubella syndrome	
Fetal alcohol syndrome	
Non-immune fetal hydrops	
Haemangioma	
Lymphangioma	
Congenital skin disorders	
Other & unspecified anomalies	Please describe
Lateral anomalies	
Teratogenic syndromes with malformations	

1. Date of diagnosis of the malformation	
2. Hospital admission?	
3. Admitting diagnosis:	
4. Discharge diagnosis:	

Condition A

Alterations in external anatomy visible at the time of **live birth** and persistent beyond the immediate **peripartum period** unless surgically repaired.

- Yes, then answer condition D
- No

Condition B

Alterations in external anatomy visible in a **stillbirth** or in the products of conception of a spontaneous or **therapeutic abortion**

- Yes, then answer condition D
- No

Condition C

Alterations in external anatomy visible in a stillbirth or in the products of conception of a spontaneous or abortion. (If products of conception cannot be used for detailed morphologic exam)

- Yes, then answer condition D
- No

Condition D

D1

Confirmed by documentation of a diagnosis made by a clinician experienced in diagnosing congenital anomalies and with the highest level of morphology training for the specific setting. (geneticists, neonatologists, pathologists, or other relevant subspecialists)

- Yes
- No

D2

Confirmed by documentation of a diagnosis made by a clinician with some experience diagnosing congenital anomalies. (physicians, nurse practitioners, or physician assistants trained in pediatrics, obstetrics, or family medicine)

- Yes
- No

D3

Confirmed by documentation of a diagnosis made by a trained maternal or child healthcare provider with at least minimal experience diagnosing congenital anomalies

- Yes
- No

Condition E

For live births, confirmed using individual (ICD-9/ICD-10) codes or as part of an ICD-9/ICD-10 code based algorithm, where the outcome (individual code or algorithm) was validated

- Yes
- No

Level 1	[YES to A OR B] AND [YES to D1]
Level 2	[YES to A OR B] AND [YES to D2]
Level 3	[YES to A OR C] AND [YES to D3 OR E]
Level 4	Reported as a case but fails to meet any level of certainty

Table 8. Major major internal structural congenital anomalies data abstraction form

Is the case tagged with internal structural congenital anomalies?

- Yes, then answer the following question and use sheet 1
- No

If yes, please select at least one of the items listed below :

Congenital heart defects	
Aortic valve stenosis	
Common truncus (truncus arteriosus or TA)	
Transposition of great vessels	
Tetralogy of Fallot	
Interrupted aortic arch (IAA)	
Double outlet right ventricle (DORV)	
Common ventricle (Single ventricle)	
Ventricular septal defect	
Atrial septal defect	
Atrioventricular septal defect (Endocardial cushion defects)	

Tricuspid valve atresia and stenosis	
Mitral valve anomalies	
Other septal closure defects	
Heart valve anomalies	
Pulmonary valve atresia and stenosis	
Hypoplastic left heart syndrome	
Hypoplastic right heart	
Ebstein anomaly	
Other heart anomalies	
Circulatory system anomalies	
Coarctation of aorta	
Patent ductus arteriosus	
Other anomalies of aorta	
Total anomalous pulmonary venous connection (TAPVC)	
Pulmonary artery anomalies	
Patent Ductus Arteriosus as only CHD in term infants (>=37 weeks)	
Situs inversus	
Other circulatory system anomalies	Please describe
Respiratory system anomalies	
Nose anomalies	
Lung agenesis & hypoplasia	
Cystic adenomatous malformation of lung	
Other respiratory system anomalies	Please describe
Choanal atresia	
Cleft lip and palate	
Cleft palate alone (without cleft lip)	
Cleft lip alone (without cleft palate)	
Cleft palate with cleft lip	

Digestive system anomalies	
tracheo-esophageal fistula, esophageal atresia & stenosis	
Biliary atresia	
Other upper alimentary tract anomalies	Please describe
Intestinal, anorectal atresia & stenosis	
rectal and large intestinal atresia/stenosis	
duodenal atresia or stenosis	
small intestinal atresia/stenosis	
Pyloric stenosis	
Hirschsprung disease	
Atresia of bile ducts	
Annular pancreas	
Other digestive system anomalies	Please describe
Urinary system anomalies	
Renal agenesis/hypoplasia & dysgenesis	
Congenital posterior urethral valves	
Undescended testicle	
Vesico-ureteric reflux	
Cystic kidney disease	
Multicystic renal dysplasia	
Congenital hydronephrosis	
Other urinary system anomalies	Please describe
Musculoskeletal anomalies	
Certain musculoskeletal anomalies	
Congenital dislocation of hip/developmental dysplasia of hip	
Diaphragmatic hernia	
Other selected congenital anomalies	
Congenital syphilis syndrome	

Congenital rubella syndrome	
Maternal infections resulting in malformations	
Fetal alcohol syndrome	
Valproate syndrome	
Non-immune fetal hydrops	
Haemangioma	
Lymphangioma	
Vascular disruption anomalies	
VATER/VACTERL defects	
Other and unspecified anomalies	Please describe

1. Date of diagnosis of the malformation	
2. Hospital admission?	
3. Admitting diagnosis:	
4. Discharge diagnosis:	

Condition A

Alterations in internal anatomy present at the time of **live birth*** and persistent beyond the immediate peripartum period unless surgically repaired

- Yes, then answer condition F
- No

Condition B

Alterations in internal anatomy detected during autopsy for a **stillbirth, spontaneous or therapeutic abortion** confirmed by documentation by a pathologist or other relevant subspecialist.

- Yes
- No

Condition C

For **stillbirth, spontaneous or therapeutic abortion**, internal structural defect was visible by ultrasound or other imaging modality prenatally

- Yes, then answer condition F
- No

Condition D

Alterations in internal anatomy present at the time of stillbirth, spontaneous abortion, or induced abortion.

- Yes, then answer condition F
- No

Condition E

For live births, confirmed using individual (ICD-9/ICD-10) codes or as part of an ICD-9/ICD-10 code based algorithm, where the outcome (individual code or algorithm) has been validated

- Yes
- No

Condition F

F1

Confirmed by definitive imaging study or intraoperative diagnosis

- Yes
- No

F2

Confirmed by documentation of a diagnosis made by a clinician experienced in diagnosing congenital anomalies and with the highest level of morphology training for the specific setting without definitive imaging or intraoperative evaluation. (geneticists, neonatologists, pathologists, or other relevant specialists)

- Yes
- No

F3

Confirmed by documentation of a diagnosis made by a clinician with some experience diagnosing congenital anomalies (physicians, nurse practitioners, or physician assistants trained in pediatrics, obstetrics, or family medicine)

- Yes
- No

Level 1	[YES to A] AND [YES to F1 OR B]
Level 2	[YES to A] AND [YES to F2 OR C]
Level 3	[YES to A] AND [YES to F3 OR E]
Level 4	Reported as a case but fails to meet any level of certainty

Table 9. Major functional congenital anomalies data abstraction form

Is the case tagged with functional congenital anomalies?

- Yes, then answer the following question and use sheet 1
- No

If yes, please select at least one of the items listed below :

Down syndrome	
Trisomy 13	
Trisomy 18	
Deletion 22 q11	
Autosomal syndromes	
Other sex chromosome conditions	Please describe
Turner syndrome	
Klinefelter syndrome	
Fragile X syndrome	
Achondroplasia	
Osteogenesis imperfecta	
Genetic syndromes + microdeletions	
Other & unspecified anomalies	Please describe
Congenital hypothyroidism	
Phenylketonuria	
Galactosaemia	
Albinism	
Cystic fibrosis	
Other metabolic disorders	
Hematological/Immune	
Haemolytic anaemias	
Thalassaemias	
Down syndrome	
Coagulation defects	

1. Date of diagnosis of the malformation	
2. Hospital admission?	
3. Admitting diagnosis:	
4. Discharge diagnosis:	

Condition A

Alterations in functioning of one or more organs or body parts for live birth:

- -Not due to a structural defect
- -Present at the time of birth (or propensity to develop alteration present at live birth)
- -Persistent beyond the immediate peripartum period, unless treated through gene therapy or stem cell transplantation
 - Yes, then answer condition C
 - No

Condition B

Alterations in functioning of one or more organs or body parts, not due to a structural defect for a ***stillbirth, spontaneous or therapeutic abortion***

- Yes, then answer condition C
- No

Condition C

C1

Confirmed by definitive diagnostic study

- Yes
- No

C2

Confirmed by documentation of a diagnosis made by a clinician experienced in diagnosing congenital anomalies and with the highest level of training in the diagnosis of functional defects for the specific setting (geneticists, neonatologists, pathologists, or other relevant subspecialists)

- Yes
- No

C3

Confirmed by documentation of a diagnosis made by a clinician with some experience diagnosing functional defects (physicians, nurse practitioners, or physician assistants trained in pediatrics, obstetrics, or family medicine)

- Yes
- No

Condition D

Confirmed using individual (ICD-9/ICD-10) codes or as part of an ICD-9/ICD-10 code-based algorithm, where the outcome (individual code or algorithm) has been validated

- Yes
- No

Level 1	[YES to A OR B] AND [YES to C1]
Level 2	[YES to A OR B] AND [YES to C2]
Level 3	[YES to A OR B] AND [YES to C3 OR D]
Level 4	Reported as a case but failed to meet any level of certainty

9. Narcolepsy

The BC case definition for narcolepsy used was:

Francesca Poli, Sebastiaan Overeem, Gert Jan Lammers, Giuseppe Plazzi, Michel Lecendreux, Claudio L. Bassetti, Yves Dauvilliers, Daniel Keene, Ramin Khatami, Yulin Li, Geert Mayer, Hanna Nohynek, Barbara Pahud, Teresa Paiva, Markku Partinen, Thomas E. Scammell, Tom Shimabukuro, Miriam Sturkenboom, Kristy van Dinther, Max Wiznitzer, Jan Bonhoeffer. Narcolepsy as an adverse event following immunization: Case definition and guidelines for data collection, analysis and presentation. *Vaccine*. 2013;31(6):994-1007. doi: 10.1016/j.vaccine.2012.12.014.

The data collection form below was taken from this case definition without any modifications.

Table 10. Narcolepsy data abstraction form

1. Date of illness onset	
2. Hospital admission?	
3. Admitting diagnosis:	
4. Discharge diagnosis:	
A. CSF hypocretin-1 deficiency	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Hypocretin-1 concentration below 110 pg/mL in crude, unextracted CSF 2. Measured by the Phoenix radioimmunoassay 3. Performed in a laboratory according to published guidelines and by using the Stanford reference sample^{1,2} 4. Not done, or unknown if done, or done but unknown in results
B-1 Excessive daytime sleepiness	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Unintended sleep episodes during the day 2. Present almost daily for at least one month 3. An increase in daytime sleep episodes 4. Present almost daily for at least one month
B-2 Unambiguous cataplexy	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sudden AND unexpected onset of episodes 2. Partial or generalised muscle weakness 3. Preserved consciousness 4. Clear emotional trigger in ≥ 2 episodes 5. Duration of < 30 s 6. Episodes with documented, reversible areflexia 7. Partial or generalised seizure 8. Neuromuscular disorders^a 9. Loss of muscle tone, e.g., falling during routine activity (i.e. while walking or running), wide-based gait, head droops, prominent facial involvement resulting in “cataplectic facies,” eyelid ptosis, mouth opening, tongue protrusion, facial weakness, facial grimacing, abnormal postures, swaying of the head and trunk, stereotypic movements or chorea-like patterns. Hypotonia and wide-based gait may also be disclosed at neurological examination 10. Duration of episodes is a few seconds to several minutes (sometimes present in protracted clusters if emotional triggers continue) 11. Any other known explanation
C. MSLT ^b (Multi Sleep Latency Test)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. MSLT mean sleep latency ≤ 8 min in adults OR MSLT mean sleep latency ≤ 12 min in children and adolescents 2. MSLT- SOREMP ≥ 2

CRITERIA	Criterion = Yes(Y) if:
CSF hypocretin-1 deficiency	A1 and A2 and A3: Yes
Excessive daytime sleepiness In adults (≥16 years)	B-1.1 and B-1.2: Yes
Excessive daytime sleepiness In children and adolescents (<16 years)	B-1.3, B-1.4: Yes
Unambiguous cataplexy in adults (≥16 years)	B-2.1, B-2.2, B-2.3, B-2.4, B-2.5: Yes and B-2.7, B-2.8: No
	B-2.1, B-2.6, B-2.5: Yes and B-2.7, B-2.8: No
Unambiguous cataplexy in children and adolescents (<16 years) ⁴	Episodes of cataplexy that fulfill the criteria for adult cataplexy
	B-2.1, B-2.3, B-2.9, B-2.10: Yes and B-2.7, B-2.8, B-2.11: NO
MSLT	C1 or C2: Yes

Level 1	YES to A and YES to B1 or B2
Level 2	B1 = YES and B2 = YES and C= YES
Level 3	B1 = YES and C1= YES and C2=Yes
Level4	If there is insufficient information to determine the conditions needed to a level of certainty of 1, 2 or 3 and X= No
Level 5 (Not a case)	If there is insufficient information to determine the conditions needed to a level of certainty of 1, 2 or 3 and X= YES

X: All levels AND in the absence of other mimicking disorders:

According to ICSD-2 criteria:

- sleep related disorder breathing
- behaviorally induced insufficient sleep
- circadian rhythm disorders
- recurrent hypersomnias secondary to medical or psychiatric conditions
- use of sedating medication and antidepressants
- focal cerebral lesions, indicated by neurological examination and/or brain imaging

a: symptoms: muscular weakness, muscular cramps, breathing difficulties, swallowing difficulties

- muscle pain,

Classification of neuromuscular disorders:

1. Motor neuron disease
2. Neuropathy

- 3. Neuromuscular junction disorders: like myasthenia gravis
 - 4. muscular dystrophies
- b:** 4 or 5 nap MSLT performed according to the American Academy of Sleep Medicine (AASM) protocol⁶

10. Cerebral venous sinus thrombosis

The VAC4EU J&J COVID-19 vaccine study has developed a case definition that support the validation of the events of CVST identified in the study.

As of March 2023, there appears to be no standard case definition to study CVST following vaccination. The approach proposed to validate this outcome will use a 365-day clean look-back period to define “new” diagnoses.

Table 11. CVST data abstraction form

Confirmation of CVST	A-1 Pathologic findings from autopsy	<p>Check the one best answer and provide details as appropriate:</p> <input type="checkbox"/> 1. Autopsy showed presence of CVST: (give date of autopsy and brief description in terms of the pathologic proof of CVST if present)
	A-2 Surgical procedure	<p>Check the one best answer and provide added details as appropriate:</p> <input type="checkbox"/> 1. Endovascular thrombectomy performed <input type="checkbox"/> 2. Other or unspecified procedure done that confirmed presence of CVST* <input type="checkbox"/> 3. No surgical procedure done; or done but either did not confirm presence of CVST or findings unknown; or unknown if done * If 2 checked, provide available details: _____
	A-3 Imaging studies confirmed the presence of CVST	<p>A-3.1 Choose the one best answer</p> <input type="checkbox"/> 1. ≥1 imaging study was done and confirmed a CVST (if yes answer A-3.2 below) <input type="checkbox"/> 2. ≥1 Imaging study was done but didn't confirm CVST <input type="checkbox"/> 3. No imaging studies done, unknown if done, or done but results unknown
		<p>A-3.2 If option 1 chosen for A-3.1, which studies confirmed a CVST? Check all that apply</p> <input type="checkbox"/> 1. Computerized tomography (CT) with contrast enhanced venography <input type="checkbox"/> 2. MRI with contrast enhanced venography <input type="checkbox"/> 3. Non-contrast CT or MRI <input type="checkbox"/> 4. Catheter-based angiography <input type="checkbox"/> 5. Other – Describe: _____
		A-3.3 Describe location(s) of the CVST based on imaging study recorded in A-3.2:

Criterion B: Clinical evidence for presence of a CVST	B-1 Reported CVST syndrome	Choose the one best answer: <input type="checkbox"/> 1. CVST was reported. (If yes, answer B-1.2 below) <input type="checkbox"/> 2. There was no report of a recognized CVST
	B-2 New onset clinical symptoms or signs that could suggest a CVST	Check all that apply: <input type="checkbox"/> 1. Acute or subacute headache <input type="checkbox"/> 2. Periorbital and forehead pain <input type="checkbox"/> 3. Ocular chemosis <input type="checkbox"/> 2. Loss of, or change in, level of consciousness <input type="checkbox"/> 3. Seizure(s) <input type="checkbox"/> 4. Fluctuating focal neurologic abnormalities (e.g., facial paralysis, difficulty with speech, ataxic gait, hemiparesis, abnormal eye movements, blurred vision or seeing double) <input type="checkbox"/> 5. Papilledema <input type="checkbox"/> 6. Bilateral cranial nerve palsies (third, fourth, fifth and/or sixth cranial nerves) <input type="checkbox"/> 7. None of the above were present or it is unknown if any of 1-6 were present
Criterion X: Alternative diagnosis	Choose the best answer <input type="checkbox"/> 1. An alternative diagnosis was found that explained the acute illness, describe: _____ 2. No alternative diagnosis was found to explain the acute illness	

CRITERIA	CRITERION OPTIONS			Criterion Value
	Criterion=YES (Y) IF:	Criterion=NO (N) IF:	Criterion=UNKNOWN (U) IF:	
CVST: A-1: Confirmed by pathology	__A-1 = 1	__A-1 = 2	__A-1 = 3	A-1 = Y U
A-2: Confirmed by surgical procedure	__A-2 = 1 - 2	__A-2 = 3		A-2 = Y N
A-3: Confirmed by imaging.	__A-3.1 = 1 and A-3.2 = ≥ 1 of (1-4)	__A3.1 = 2	__A-3.1 = 3	A-3 = Y N
B-1: CVST syndrome reported	__B-1 = 1	__B-1 = 2		B-1 = Y U
B-2: ≥ 1 clinical symptom or sign	__B-2 ≥ 1 of (1-6)	__B-2 = 7		B-2 = Y N
X. Alternative diagnosis	__X = 1	__X = 2	Not applicable	X = Y N

Level of Certainty	
Level 1	A-1 OR A-2 OR A-3 = YES
Level 2	[B-1 AND B-2= YES] AND X = NO
Level 3	[B-1 = YES] or [B-2 \geq 3] AND X = NO
Level 4a	Not applicable
Level 4b	Reported as a case of CVST but fails to meet any level of certainty
Level 5	An alternative diagnosis to account for the clinical illness was found (X = YES)

11. Deep Vein Thrombosis (DVT)

The VAC4EU J&J COVID-19 vaccine study has developed a case definition that support the validation of the events of DVT identified in the study.

As of March 2023, there appears to be no standard case definition to study DVT following vaccination. The approach proposed to validate this outcome will follow the same approach used for DVT as a component of TTS. It will use a 365-day clean look-back period to define “new” diagnoses.

Table 12. DVT data abstraction form

Criterion A Confirmation of DVT	A-1 Pathologic findings from autopsy	<p>Check the one best answer and provide details as appropriate:</p> <input type="checkbox"/> 1. Autopsy showed presence of DVT: (give date of autopsy and brief description in terms of the pathologic proof of DVT or both if present)
	A-2 Surgical procedure	<p>Check the one best answer and provide added details as appropriate:</p> <input type="checkbox"/> 1. Thrombectomy related to DVT performed*
	A-3 Imaging studies confirmed the presence of DVT	<p>Check the one best answer and provide details as appropriate:</p> <input type="checkbox"/> 2. Autopsy done but showed no evidence of DVT
		<input type="checkbox"/> 3. No autopsy done, unknown if done, or done but results unavailable.
		<input type="checkbox"/> 1. Thrombectomy related to DVT performed*
		<input type="checkbox"/> 2. Other procedure done that confirmed presence of DVT*
		<input type="checkbox"/> 3. No surgical procedure done; or, done but either did not confirm presence of DVT or findings unknown; or unknown if done
		<p>* If 1 or 2 checked describe procedure, location and finding:</p>
	A-3.1 Choose the one best answer	<input type="checkbox"/> 1. ≥ 1 imaging study was done and confirmed DVT (if yes answer A-3.2 below)
		<input type="checkbox"/> 2. ≥ 1 Imaging study was done but didn't confirm DVT
		<input type="checkbox"/> 3. No imaging studies done, unknown if done, or done but results unknown
	A-3.2 If option 1 chosen for A-3.1, which studies confirmed DVT? Check all that apply	<input type="checkbox"/> 1. Compression ultrasonography
		<input type="checkbox"/> 2. CT or MR venography
		<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Contrast venography
		<input type="checkbox"/> 4. Doppler/Duplex Ultrasound
		<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Other – Describe:
	A-3.2 Describe location(s) of DVT based on imaging study:	
Criterion B: Clinical evidence for presence of DVT	B-1.1 Signs and symptoms of DVT reported	<p>Choose the one best answer:</p> <input type="checkbox"/> 1. ≥ 1 symptom or sign of DVT was reported. (If yes, answer B-1.2 and B2 below)
	B-1.2 Specific type(s) of DVT	<p>Check all that apply:</p> <input type="checkbox"/> 2. There was no report of a recognized DVT syndrome
	B-2 New onset clinical symptoms or signs that could suggest DVT	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. It is unknown if there was a report of a DVT syndrome
		<input type="checkbox"/> 1. Lower extremity DVT
		<input type="checkbox"/> 2. Upper extremity DVT
		<p>Check all that apply:</p> <input type="checkbox"/> 1. Calf pain or tenderness
		<input type="checkbox"/> 2. leg swelling or pitting edema
		<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Absent pulses in legs or arms
		<input type="checkbox"/> 4. Redness, warmth, or pain in one or more extremities
		<input type="checkbox"/> 5. None of the above were present or it is unknown if any of 1-4 were present

Criterion C D-Dimer	<p>Choose the one best answer:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 1. D-dimer exceeded test lab's upper limit of normal. What was the highest measured value within 2 weeks before and 2 weeks after the date of the event under validation? _____ If known, please indicate the test lab's upper limit of normal:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 2. D-dimer tested and was within test lab's range of normal</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 3. D-dimer not tested, or tested but results unknown or not available</p>
Condition F	<p>Reported as a case of DVT by specialist, without details</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
Criterion X: Alternative diagnosis	<p>Choose the one best answer</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 1. An alternative diagnosis was found that explained the acute illness. describe: _____</p> <p>2. No alternative diagnosis was found to explain the acute illness</p>

CRITERIA	CRITERION OPTIONS			Criterion Value
	Criterion=YES (Y) IF:	Criterion=NO (N) IF:	Criterion=UNKNOWN (U) IF:	
A-1: Confirmed by pathology	__ A-1 = 1	__ A-1 = 2	__ A-1 = 3	A-1 = Y N U
A-2: Confirmed by surgery	__ A-2 = 1 or 2	__ A-2 = 3		A-2 = Y N/U
A-3: Confirmed by imaging.	__ A-3.1 = 1	__ A3.1 = 2	__ A-3.1 = 3	A-3 = Y N U
B-1: DVT syndrome reported	__ B-1.1 = 1 AND B-1.2 = ≥1 of (1-2)	__ B-1.1 = 2	__ B-1.1 = 3	B-1 = Y N U
B-2: ≥1 clinical symptom or sign	__ B-2 = ≥1 of (1-4)	__ B-2 = 5		B-2 = Y N/U
C. D-Dimer >test lab's upper normal limit	__ C = 1	__ C = 2	__ C = 3	C = Y N U
X. Alternative diagnosis	__ X = 1	__ X = 2	Not applicable	X = Y N

Level of Certainty	
Level 1	(A-1 OR A-2 OR A-3 = YES) and X = NO or X = Not applicable
Level 2	[B-1 or B-2 = YES] AND [C = YES] AND X = NO
Level 3	[B-1 or B-2 = YES] AND X = NO
Level4-A	If there is insufficient information to determine the conditions needed to a level of certainty of 1, 2 or 3 and F = Yes then the level of certainty is level 4a and x=No?
Level 4-B	If there is insufficient information to determine the conditions needed to a level of certainty of 1, 2 or 3 and F = NO then the level of certainty is level 4a and x=No
Level 5	An alternative diagnosis to account for the clinical illness was found (X = YES)

12. Pulmonary Embolism (PE)

The VAC4EU J&J COVID-19 vaccine study has developed a case definition that support the validation of the events of PE identified in the study.

As of March 2023, there appears to be no standard case definition to study PE following vaccination. The approach proposed to validate this outcome will follow the same approach used for PE as a component of TTS. It will use a 365-day clean look-back period to define “new” diagnoses.

Table 13. PE data abstraction form

Criterion A Confirmation of PE	A-1 Pathologic findings from biopsy or autopsy	Check the one best answer and provide details as appropriate: <input type="checkbox"/> 1. Biopsy showed presence of PE <input type="checkbox"/> 2. Autopsy showed presence of PE: (give date of autopsy and brief description in terms of the pathologic proof of PE) <input type="checkbox"/> 3. Biopsy or autopsy done but showed no evidence of PE <input type="checkbox"/> 4. No biopsy or autopsy done, unknown if done, or done but results unavailable.
	A-2 Surgical procedure	Check the one best answer and provide added details as appropriate: <input type="checkbox"/> 1. Thrombectomy performed* <input type="checkbox"/> 2. Other procedure done that confirmed presence of PE* <input type="checkbox"/> 3. No surgical procedure done; or, done but either did not confirm presence of PE or findings unknown; or unknown if done * If 1 or 2 checked describe procedure, location and finding:
	A-3 Imaging studies confirmed	A-3.1 Choose the one best answer <input type="checkbox"/> 1. ≥1 imaging study was done and confirmed PE (if yes answer A-3.2 below) <input type="checkbox"/> 2. ≥1 Imaging study was done but didn't confirm PE <input type="checkbox"/> 3. No imaging studies done, unknown if done, or done but results unknown

	the presence of PE	<p>A-3.2 If option 1 chosen for A-3.1, which studies confirmed PE? Check all that apply</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 1. Echocardiogram</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 2. CT pulmonary angiography</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 3. Ventilation-Perfusion (V/Q) scan (Ventilation-Perfusion scintigraphy)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 4. Pulmonary angiography</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 5. Other – Describe:</p> <p>A-3.3 Describe location(s) of thrombosis/thromboembolism based on imaging study:</p>
Criterion B: Clinical evidence for presence of PE	B-1 Signs and symptoms of PE reported	<p>Choose the one best answer:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 1. ≥ 1 sign or symptom of PE was reported (if yes, answer B-2 below)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 2. There was no report of recognized PE signs or symptoms</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 3. It is unknown if there was a report of PE signs or symptoms</p>
	B-2 New onset clinical symptoms or signs that could suggest PE	<p>Check all that apply:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 1 Sudden shortness of breath</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 2. Chest pain</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 3. Tachypnea⁽¹⁾</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 4. Tachycardia⁽²⁾</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 5. Cyanosis</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 6. Hypotension</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 7. Sudden unexpected death</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 8. None of the above were present or it is unknown if any of 1-8 were present.</p>
Criterion C D-Dimer		<p>Choose the one best answer:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 1. D-dimer exceeded test lab's upper limit of normal. What was the highest measured value within 2 weeks before and 2 weeks after the date of the event under validation: If known, please indicate the test lab's upper limit of normal:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 2. D-dimer tested and was within test lab's range of normal</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 3. D-dimer not tested, or tested but results unknown or not available</p>
Criterion D: Imaging studies that supported but did not confirm the presence of PE	D-1 Chest radiograph (CXR)	<p>Choose the one best answer:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 1. CXR done and showed ≥ 1 of the following: wedge shaped opacity; pleural effusion; prominent proximal pulmonary artery with reduction in peripheral vessel markings</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 2. CXR done and was normal or had none of the findings listed in choice 1 above</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 3. CXR was not done or CXR done but results unknown</p>

	<p>D-2 Transthoracic Echocardiogram (T-Echo)</p>	<p>Choose the one best answer</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 1. T-Echo was done and showed ≥ 1 of the following: right heart dilation; tricuspid regurgitation; interventricular septal compression; or right ventricular hypokinesia.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 2. T-echo was done and was normal or had none of the findings listed in choice 1 above</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 3. T-echo was not done, or T-echo done but results unknown.</p>
	<p>D-3 non-contrast computed tomography (CT)</p>	<p>Choose the one best answer:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 1. Non-contrast chest CT was done and showed ≥ 1 of the following: wedge shaped opacity; pleural effusion; prominent proximal pulmonary artery with reduction in peripheral vessel markings</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 2. Non-contrast CT was done and was normal or had none of the findings listed in choice 1.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 3. Non-contrast CT not done or done but results unknown.</p>
	<p>D-4 Evidence of limb DVT</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> 1. Imaging test confirmed presence of DVT</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 2. Imaging tests to diagnose DVT conducted but did not confirm presence of DVT</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 3. Imaging tests to diagnose DVT were not conducted or results are unknown</p>
<p>Condition F:</p>	<p>Reported as a case of TTS by specialist, without details</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> No</p>	
<p>Criterion X: Alternative diagnosis</p>	<p>Choose the one best answer</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 1. An alternative diagnosis was found that explained the acute illness, describe: _____</p> <p>2. No alternative diagnosis was found to explain the acute illness</p>	

CRITERIA	CRITERION OPTIONS			Criterion
	Criterion=YES (Y) IF:	Criterion=NO (N) IF:	Criterion=UNKNOWN (U) IF:	Value
Pulmonary Embolism: A-1: Confirmed by pathology	_A-1 = 1 or 2	_A-1 = 3	_A-1 = 4	A-1 = Y N U
A-2: Confirmed by surgery	_A-2 = 1 or 2	_A-2 = 3		A-2 = Y N/U
A-3: Confirmed by imaging	_A-3.1 = 1 AND A-3.2 ≥ 1 of (1-5)	_A3.1 = 2	_A-3.1 = 3	A-3 = Y N U
B-1: PE signs and symptoms reported	_B-1.1 = 1	_B-1.1 = 2	_B-1.1 = 3	B-1 = Y N U
B-2: ≥1 non-specific clinical symptom or sign	_B-2 = ≥1 of (1-8)	_B-2 = 9		B-2 = Y N/U
C. D-Dimer >test lab's upper normal limit	_C = 1	_C = 2	_C = 3	C = Y N U
D. Imaging studies supported but couldn't confirm PE	_(D-1 = 1) or (D-2 = 1) or (D-3 = 1) or (D-4 = 1)	_(D-1 = 2 or 3) and (D-2 = 2 or 3) and (D-3 = 2 or 3) and (D-4 = 2 or 3)		D = Y N/U
X. Alternative diagnosis	_X = 1	_X = 2	Not applicable	X = Y N

Level of Certainty	
Level 1	A-1 OR A-2 OR A-3 = YES
Level 2	[B-1 or B-2 = YES] AND [C AND D = YES] AND X = NO
Level 3	[B-1 or B-2 = YES] AND X = NO
Level 4-A	If there is insufficient information to determine the conditions needed to a level of certainty of 1, 2 or 3 and E = Yes then the level of certainty and X=NO is level 4-A
Level 4-B	If there is insufficient information to determine the conditions needed to a level of certainty of 1, 2 or 3 and E = NO then the level of certainty and X=NO is Level 4-B
Level 5	An alternative diagnosis to account for the clinical illness was found (X = YES)

13. Hemorrhagic Stroke (acute intracerebral hemorrhage)

The VAC4EU J&J COVID-19 vaccine study has developed a case definition that support the validation of the events of hemorrhagic stroke identified in the study.

As of March 2023, there appears to be no standard case definition to study hemorrhagic stroke following vaccination. The approach proposed to validate this outcome will use a 365-day clean look-back period to define “new” diagnoses.

Table 14. Hemorrhagic stroke data abstraction form

Confirmation of hemorrhagic stroke	A-1 Pathologic findings from autopsy	Check the one best answer and provide details as appropriate: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Autopsy showed presence of hemorrhagic stroke: (give date of autopsy and brief description in terms of the pathologic proof of acute intracerebral hemorrhage if present) 2. Autopsy done but did not show evidence of hemorrhagic stroke 3. No autopsy done, unknown if done, or done but results unavailable.
	A-2 Surgical procedure	Check the one best answer and provide added details as appropriate: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. External ventricular drain 2. Surgical hematoma evacuation 3. Decompressive craniotomy with or without hematoma evacuation 4. Minimally invasive surgery 5. Surgical procedure unspecified but confirms hemorrhagic stroke 6. No surgical procedure done; or, done but either did not confirm presence of acute intracerebral hemorrhage or findings unknown; or unknown if done
	A-3 Imaging studies confirmed the presence of hemorrhagic stroke	<p>A-3.1 Choose the one best answer</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. ≥1 imaging study was done and confirmed a hemorrhagic stroke (if yes answer A-3.2 below) 2. ≥1 Imaging study was done but didn't confirm hemorrhagic stroke 3. No imaging studies done, unknown if done, or done but results unknown <p>A-3.2 If option 1 chosen for A-3.1, which studies confirmed a hemorrhagic stroke? Check all that apply</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Non-contrast computerized tomography (CT) 2. MRI 3. CT or MRI angiography 4. Other – Describe: <p>A-3.3 Describe location(s) of the hemorrhagic stroke based on imaging study recorded in A-3.2:</p>
Criterion B: Clinical evidence for presence of hemorrhagic stroke	B-1 Reported hemorrhagic stroke	Choose the one best answer: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. A hemorrhagic stroke was reported. (If yes, answer B-2 below) 2. There was no report of a recognized hemorrhagic stroke
	B-2 New onset clinical symptoms or signs that could suggest a syndrome	Check all that apply: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sudden headache 2. Loss of, or change in, level of consciousness 3. Seizure(s)

	hemorrhagic stroke	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4. Focal neurologic abnormalities (e.g., facial paralysis, difficulty with speech, ataxic gait, hemiparesis, abnormal eye movements, blurred vision or seeing double) • 5. Mention of elevated blood pressure 48h before and after the date of the event (provide value of highest systolic and diastolic blood pressure, if available: _____ mmHg / _____ mmHg) <p>6. None of the above were present or it is unknown if any of 1-5 were present</p>
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<p>Criterion X: Alternative diagnosis</p>	<p>Choose the best answer</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1. An alternative diagnosis was found that explained the acute illness, describe: _____ • 2. No alternative diagnosis was found to explain the acute illness
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CRITERIA	CRITERION OPTIONS			Criterion Value
	Criterion=YES (Y) IF:	Criterion=NO (N) IF:	Criterion=UNKNOWN (U) IF:	
Ischemic stroke: A-1: Confirmed by pathology	__A-1 = 1	__A-1 = 2	__A-1 = 3	A-1 = Y N U
A-2: Confirmed by surgery	__A-2 = 1 - 5	__A-2 = 6		A-2 = Y N/U
A-3: Confirmed by imaging.	__A-3.1 = 1 and __A-3.2 = ≥1 of (1-4)	__A3.1 = 2	__A-3.1 = 3	A-3 = Y N U
B-1: hemorrhagic stroke reported	__B-1 = 1	__B-1 = 2		B-1 = Y N U
B-2: ≥1 clinical symptom or sign	__B-2 ≥1 of (1-5)	__B-2 = 6		B-2 = Y N/U
X. Alternative diagnosis	__X = 1	__X = 2	Not applicable	X = Y N

Level of Certainty	
Level 1	A-1 OR A-2 OR A-3 = YES
Level 2	[B-1 AND B-2= YES] AND X = NO
Level 3	[B-1 = YES] AND X = NO
Level 4a	Not applicable
Level 4b	Reported as a case of hemorrhagic stroke but fails to meet any level of certainty
Level 5	An alternative diagnosis to account for the clinical illness was found (X = YES)

14. Ischemic stroke

The VAC4EU J&J COVID-19 vaccine study has developed a case definition that support the validation of the events of ischemic stroke identified in the study.

As of March 2023, there appears to be no standard case definition to study ischemic stroke following vaccination. The approach proposed to validate this outcome will use a 365-day clean look-back period to define “new” diagnoses.

Table 15. stroke data abstraction form

Confirmation of ischemic stroke	A-1 Pathologic findings from autopsy or biopsy	<p>Check the one best answer and provide details as appropriate:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Autopsy showed presence of ischemic stroke: (give date of autopsy and brief description in terms of the pathologic proof of thrombosis or thromboembolism or both if present) 2. Autopsy done but did not show ischemic stroke 3. No autopsy done, unknown if done, or done but results unavailable.
	A-2 Surgical procedure	<p>Check the one best answer and provide added details as appropriate:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Thrombectomy performed* 2. Other or unspecified procedure done that confirmed the presence of cerebral artery thrombosis or thromboembolism* 3. No surgical procedure done; or, done but either did not confirm presence of cerebral artery thrombosis or thromboembolism or findings unknown; or unknown if done <p>* If 1 or 2 checked describe procedure, location and finding:</p> <p>_____</p> <p>_____</p>
	A-3 Imaging studies confirmed the presence of ischemic stroke	<p>A-3.1 Choose the one best answer</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. ≥1 imaging study was done and confirmed an ischemic stroke (if yes answer A-3.2 below) 2. ≥1 Imaging study was done but didn't confirm ischemic stroke 3. No imaging studies done, unknown if done, or done but results unknown <p>A-3.2 If option 1 chosen for A-3.1, which studies confirmed an ischemic stroke? Check all that apply</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Diffusion weighted MRI 2. CT or MRI angiography 3. Ultrasound (carotid of transcranial Doppler) 4. Perfusion CT or MRI 5. Positron emission tomography (PET)) 6. Other – Describe:

		A-3.3 Describe location(s) of the ischemic stroke based on imaging study:
Criterion B: Clinical evidence for presence of an ischemic stroke	New onset clinical symptoms or signs that could suggest an ischemic stroke	Check all that apply: 1. Sudden painless loss of vision 2. Loss of, or change in, level of consciousness 3. Seizure(s) 4. Focal neurologic abnormalities (e.g., facial paralysis, difficulty with speech, ataxic gait, hemiparesis, abnormal eye movements, blurred vision or seeing double) 5. None of the above were present or it is unknown if any of 1-5 were present
Criterion C: Imaging studies to rule out hemorrhagic stroke	Choose the one best answer: 1. Imaging study done and showed evidence of an ischemic stroke with absence of intracranial bleeding 2. Imaging study done and showed evidence of intracranial bleeding, or no imaging study done	
Criterion D: Reported ischemic stroke	Reported as a case of ischemic stroke by specialist, without details <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No 	
Criterion X: Alternative diagnosis	Choose the one best answer 1. An alternative diagnosis was found that explained the acute illness, describe: _____ 2. No alternative diagnosis was found to explain the acute illness	

CRITERIA	CRITERION OPTIONS			Criterion Value
	Criterion=YES (Y) IF:	Criterion=NO (N) IF:	Criterion=UNKNO WN (U) IF:	
Ischemic stroke: A-1: Confirmed by pathology	__A-1 = 1	__A-1 = 2	__A-1 = 3	A-1 = Y N U
A-2: Confirmed by surgery	__A-2 = 1 or 2	__A-2 = 3		A-2 = Y N/U
A-3: Confirmed by imaging	__A-3.1 = 1 and A-3.2 ≥1 of (1-6)	__A3.1 = 2	__A-3.1 = 3	A-3 = Y N U
B: ≥1 clinical symptom or sign	__B = ≥1 of (1-4)	__B = 5		B-2 = Y N/U
D:Reported ischemic stroke	__D = 1	__D = 2		D = Y N/U
C: Imaging studies supported but couldn't confirm an ischemic stroke	__C = 1	__C = 2		D = Y N/U
X: Alternative diagnosis	__X = 1	__X = 2	Not applicable	X = Y N

Level of Certainty	
Level 1	A-1 OR A-2 OR A-3 = YES
Level 2	[B = YES] AND [C = YES] AND X = NO
Level 3	[B= YES] AND X = NO
Level 4 a	[D= YES] AND X = NO
Level 4 b	Reported as a case of ischemic stroke but fails to meet any level of certainty
Level 5	An alternative diagnosis to account for the clinical illness was found (X = YES)

15. Meningoencephalitis including ADEM

The VAC4EU J&J COVID-19 vaccine study has developed a case definition that support the validation of the events of meningoencephalitis including ADEM identified in the study.

The BC case definition for meningoencephalitis including ADEM used was

Law B. AESI Case Definition Companion Guide: Acute Disseminated Encephalomyelitis. Zenodo; 2021 Feb
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6668857>

The questionnaires for validation of this AESI are split for infectious meningoencephalitis and ADEM, because of their different pathophysiologic nature. The event will be considered to have reached the highest level of certainty achieved for the 2 components of the AESI.

Table 16. Meningoencephalitis including ADEM data abstraction form

<p>Criterion AA Confirmation of infectious meningoencephalitis</p> <p>AA-1 Pathologic findings from autopsies/Biopsy</p> <p>AA-1.1 Check the one best answer and provide details as appropriate:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 1. Autopsy / biopsy showed presence of infectious meningoencephalitis: (give date of autopsy and brief description in terms of the pathologic proof of infectious meningoencephalitis if present)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 2. Autopsy / biopsy done but showed no evidence of infectious meningoencephalitis</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 3. Autopsy / biopsy not done, unknown if done, or done but results unavailable.</p> <p>AA-2 Cerebrospinal fluid investigation confirmed the presence of infectious meningoencephalitis</p> <p>AA-2.1 Choose the one best answer</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 1. Cerebrospinal fluid investigation study was done and confirmed infectious meningoencephalitis (if yes answer AA-2.2 below)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 2. Cerebrospinal fluid investigation study was done but didn't confirm infectious meningoencephalitis</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 3. No cerebrospinal fluid investigation done, unknown if done, or done but results unknown</p> <p>AA-2.2 If option 1 chosen for AA-2.1, which was the causal agent identified for infectious meningoencephalitis?</p> <p>_____</p> <p>_____</p> <p>AA-3 Blood testing supporting the diagnosis of infectious meningoencephalitis</p> <p>AA-3.1 Choose the one best answer</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 1. Blood culture, PCR, or immunochromatographic antigen testing were done and supported the diagnosis of infectious meningoencephalitis (if yes answer AA-3.2 below)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 2. Blood culture, PCR, or immunochromatographic antigen testing were done but didn't support the diagnosis of infectious meningoencephalitis</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 3. No blood culture, PCR, or immunochromatographic antigen testing were done unknown if done, or done but results unknown</p> <p>AA-3.2 If option 1 chosen for AA-3.1, which was the causal agent identified for infectious meningoencephalitis? ____</p>		
<p>Criterion BA: Imaging studies support the diagnosis of infectious meningoencephalitis</p>	<p>BA-1 Imaging studies conducted that support the diagnosis of infectious meningoencephalitis</p>	<p>BA-1.1 Check all that apply:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 1. Brain MRI (such as T2 hyperintensity, Diffuse cerebral atrophy)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 2. Cranial CT scan</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 3. Electroencephalogram</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 4. Other imaging tests. Specify which: ____</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 5. Imaging studies conducted and did not suggest diagnosis of infectious meningoencephalitis</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 6. No imaging studies conducted or conducted but results unknown</p>
<p>Criterion CA: Clinical evidence for presence of infectious meningoencephalitis</p>	<p>CA-1 Signs and symptoms of infectious meningoencephalitis reported</p>	<p>CA-1.1 Choose the one best answer:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 1. ≥ 1 symptom or sign of infectious meningoencephalitis was reported. (If yes, answer CA-2.2 below)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 2. There was no report of a recognized an infectious meningoencephalitis syndrome</p>

		<input type="checkbox"/> 3. It is unknown if there was a report of an infectious meningoencephalitis syndrome
	CA-2 New onset clinical symptoms or signs that could suggest an infectious meningoencephalitis	CA-2.2 Check all that apply: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> 1. Fever <input type="checkbox"/> 2. Irritability <input type="checkbox"/> 3. Behavioural changes <input type="checkbox"/> 4. Meningism <input type="checkbox"/> 5. Focal neurological signs <input type="checkbox"/> 6. Seizures <input type="checkbox"/> 7. Headache <input type="checkbox"/> 8. Nausea/Vomiting <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Altered level of consciousness <input type="checkbox"/> 10. Petechial rash/purpura <input type="checkbox"/> 11. None of the above were present or it is unknown if any of 1-10 were present
Criterion XA: Alternative diagnosis	Choose the one best answer <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> 1. An alternative diagnosis was found that explained the acute illness: describe- _____ <input type="checkbox"/> 2. No alternative diagnosis was found to explain the acute illness 	

<p>Criterion AB Confirmation of ADEM</p>	<p>AB-1 Pathologic findings from autopsy/biopsy</p>	<p>AB-1.1 Check the one best answer and provide details as appropriate:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 1. Autopsy/biopsy showed presence of ADEM: (give date of autopsy and brief description in terms of the pathologic proof of ADEM if present)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 2. Autopsy/biopsy done but showed no evidence of ADEM</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 3. Autopsy/biopsy not done, unknown if done, or done but results unavailable.</p>
<p>BB-1 Imaging studies conducted that support the diagnosis of ADEM</p>	<p>BB-1.1 Check all that apply:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 1. Brain MRI (such as multiple lesions in the deep, subcortical and periventricular white matter, characteristic of demyelination)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 2. Other imaging tests. Specify which: _____</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 3. Imaging studies conducted and did not suggest diagnosis of ADEM</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 4. No imaging studies conducted or conducted but results unknown</p>	
<p>Criterion CB: Clinical evidence for presence of ADEM</p>	<p>CB-1 Signs and symptoms of ADEM reported</p>	<p>CB-1.1 Choose the one best answer:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 1. ≥ 1 symptom or sign of ADEM was reported. (If yes, answer CB-2.2 below)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 2. There was no report of a recognized ADEM syndrome</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 3. It is unknown if there was a report of a ADEM syndrome</p>
	<p>CB-2 New onset clinical symptoms or signs that could suggest an ADEM</p>	<p>CB-2.2 Check all that apply:</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 1. Ataxia</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 2. Altered level of consciousness</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 3. Brainstem symptoms (such as Balance problems or dizziness. Inability to gag or cough, Insomnia, Nausea or vomiting, Stroke symptoms. Sudden difficulty swallowing, drinking or eating.</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 4. Optic neuritis</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 5. Transverse myelitis</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 6. Seizures</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 7. Headache</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 8. Meningism</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 9. Fever</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 10. None of the above were present or it is unknown if any of 1-9 were present</p>
<p>Criterion XB: Alternative diagnosis</p>	<p>Choose the one best answer</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 1. An alternative diagnosis was found that explained the acute illness: describe- _____</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> 2. No alternative diagnosis was found to explain the acute illness</p>	

CRITERIA	CRITERION OPTIONS			Criterion Value
	Criterion=YES (Y) IF:	Criterion=NO (N) IF:	Criterion=UNKNOWN (U) IF:	
Meningoencephalitis including ADEM diagnosis: A-1: Confirmed by pathology	AA-1.1 = 1 OR AB-1.1 = 1	AA-1.1 = 2 AND AB-1.1 = 2	AA-1.1 = 3 AND AB-1.1 = 3	A-1 = Y N U
A-2: Confirmed by cerebrospinal fluid investigation	AA-2.1 = 1	AA-2.1 = 2 or 3		A-2 = Y N/U
A3: Supported by blood testing	AA-3.1 = 1	AA-3.1 = 2 or 3		A-3 = Y N/U
B-1: Imaging studies supporting meningoencephalitis including ADEM syndrome reported	BA-1.1 ≥1 of (1-4) OR BB-1.1 ≥1 of (1-2)	BA-1.1 = 5 AND BB-1.1 = 3	BA-1.1 = 6 AND BB-1.1 = 4	B-1 = Y N U
C-1. Clinical evidence for presence of meningoencephalitis including ADEM	CA-1.1 = 1 OR CB-1.1 = 1	CA-1.1 = 2 AND CB-1.1 = 2	CA-1.1 = 3 AND CB-1.1 = 3	C-1 = Y N U
C-2 New onset clinical symptoms or signs that could suggest a meningoencephalitis including ADEM	CA-2.2 = 1 to 10 OR CB-2.2 = 1 to 9	CA-2.2 =11 AND CB-2.2 =10		C-2 = Y N/U
X. Alternative diagnosis	XA = 1 OR XB = 1	XA = 2 AND XB = 2	Not applicable	X = Y N

Level of Certainty	
Level 1	A-1 OR A-2 = YES
Level 2	[A-3= YES OR B-1 = YES] AND [C-1 OR C-2 = YES] AND X = NO
Level 3	[A-3= YES OR B-1 = YES] AND [C-1 AND C-2 = NO/U] AND X = NO
Level 4	Reported as a case of meningoencephalitis including ADEM but fails to meet any level of certainty AND X = NO
Level 5	An alternative diagnosis to account for the clinical illness was found (X = YES)

16. Bleeding with Thrombocytopenia (BT)

The VAC4EU members that are part of the research team participating in the AstraZeneca COVID19 PASS aim to develop a case definition that supports the validation of the events of bleeding with thrombocytopenia identified in the study.

As of April 2023, there appears to be no standard case definition to study thrombocytopenia with bleeding following vaccination. The approach proposed to identify this outcome in automated data will follow the same approach used for TTS, using bleeding instead of thrombosis to anchor the search. It will use a 365-days clean look-back period to define “new” diagnoses. Briefly, the working case definition for thrombocytopenia with bleeding for this study requires 2 components:

- A new qualifying bleeding event (defined below) AND
- A new diagnosis of thrombocytopenia (or laboratory evidence of the same, where available) that is made from 10 days before and up to 10 days after that event

Bleeding events will include new diagnoses of clinically significant bleeds in the central nervous system, respiratory tract, gastrointestinal tract, or genitourinary tract, where “clinically significant” means requiring hospitalisation or emergency department care.

The goal of this document is to develop an electronic case report form (eCRF) to facilitate the extraction of the data from the participating databanks and determine the level of certainty of each case. The Case Definition (CD) Level of Certainty (LOC) is determined based on a series of clinical conditions defined below.

1. Date of event onset	
2. Date of Thrombocytopenia	
3. Hospital admission? (no/yes, date_)	
4. Admitting diagnosis:	
5. Discharge diagnosis:	

Condition A1: Patient required hospitalisation or emergency department visit

Condition A2: Platelet count $<150 \times 10^9/L$ of new onset with no known recent exposure to heparin (within the last 30 days)

Condition B1: Presence of bleeding confirmed by ≥ 1 of the following (Check all that apply below)

Imaging Study

Endoscopy

Colonoscopy

Ultrasound – Doppler

CT scan – contrast/ angiography/ CR Urogram/ MR Urogram

- Multidetector CT (MDCT)
- Magnetic resonance venography or arteriography
- Magnetic resonance
- Perfusion V/Q scan
- Conventional angiography / digital subtraction angiography
- Bronchoscopy
- Cystography
- No imaging studies done, unknown if done, or done but results unknown

Surgical procedure - that confirmed presence of a bleeding or repair of bleeding (e.g. drainage of subarachnoid hemorrhage)

Please describe: _____

Pathologic examination – including biopsy or autopsy

Please describe: _____

Visual evidence of bleeding

Gastrointestinal bleeding

Hematemesis

Melena

Other, please describe: _____

Genitourinary bleeding

Hematuria

Other, please describe: _____

Respiratory tract bleeding

Epistaxis

Hemorrhage from respiratory passage/hemoptysis

Cough with hemorrhage

Other, please describe:

Condition C: **Clinical presentation suggests one of the specific clinical syndromes below?** (Check the most appropriate) NOTE: the italicized signs/symptoms in brackets after each are suggestive of the syndrome but not an exhaustive list; if any of them is present you can check the item. Diagnosis of the syndrome by a clinical specialist is also acceptable

Central nervous system bleeding

Headache

Vomiting

Paralysis

Numbness

Dysarthria

- Altered mental status*
- Neck pain or nuchal rigidity*
- loss of balance*
- Blurred vision*
- Seizure*
- Motor dysfunction*
- Other, please describe: _____*
- Diagnosis by specialist without details*

Gastrointestinal bleeding

- Non-visual evidence of bleeding, please describe: _____
- Diagnosis by specialist without details*

Genitourinary bleeding

- Non-visual evidence of bleeding, please describe: _____
- Diagnosis by specialist without details*

Respiratory tract bleeding

- Pulmonary hemorrhage,*
- Shortness of breath,*
- Dyspnea,*
- Non-visual evidence of bleeding, please describe: _____
- Diagnosis by specialist without details*

Condition D: **One or more of these imaging or lab findings supportive of the diagnosis of bleeding?** (Check all that apply)

- Stool test
- Chest radiograph (CXR)
- Ultrasound scans
- Computed tomography without contrast
- Hemoglobin decreased below lower limit of normal,value_____

Condition E : **Reported as a case of Thrombocytopenia with bleeding by specialist, without details**

- Yes
- No

Condition X: **An alternative diagnosis was found that explains the acute illness** (Should not include causes or risk factors for bleeding such as hemophilia, vit k deficiency, cancer, etc...)

Describe: _____

- No alternative diagnosis was found that explains the acute illness**

BT Case Definition Level of Certainty Determination

- If yes to (A1, and A2, and B1) : then is **Level 1**
- If no to (B1) _and_ [If yes to (A1 and A2) AND yes to (C and D) AND no to (X)] then is **Level 2**

- If no to (B1) _and_ [If yes to (A1 and A2) AND yes to (C) AND no to (D, and X)] then is **Level 3**
- If there is insufficient information to determine the conditions needed to a level of certainty of 1, 2 or 3 and E = Yes then the level of certainty is level 4a
- If there is insufficient information to determine the conditions needed to a level of certainty of 1, 2 or 3 and E = NO then the level of certainty is **Level 4-B**
- If there is sufficient information to determine the conditions A, B, C, D, and X but the aggregate of the conditions do not meet the LOC 1, 2, or 3 and/or X=YES then the LOC is **Level 5**; Not a Case of hospitalisation or emergency department visit due to thrombocytopenia with bleeding